

Bachelor Degree Project

Interpretable Taxonomy-Driven
Stock-Return Forecasting on
Nasdaq Stockholm

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Abstract

Forecasting stock returns is notoriously difficult, and most machine learning papers focus on predictive accuracy while neglecting interpretability. This thesis presents a taxonomy-driven feature selection study on NASDAQ Stockholm equities (2015–2025), embedding financial theory into the modeling process. Twenty-four single-asset technical indicators are grouped into four functional families—trend, momentum, volatility, and volume—and used to guide forward selection in a BiLSTM model forecasting cumulative 10-day returns. Across experiments, volume and volatility indicators consistently provide the strongest predictive signal, while adding trend and momentum indicators often reduces out-of-sample performance. Although overall predictive accuracy remains modest and unstable, taxonomy-based grouping improves interpretability by yielding a smaller, clearer family-level specification and revealing recurring signal structures that indicator-wise selection obscures. These findings suggest that embedding domain knowledge into feature design can improve methodological transparency without materially degrading performance, and provide evidence on which technical signal families carry most information in a mid-sized European market.

Keywords: Financial Forecasting, Technical Indicators, Feature Selection, Domain-Informed Modeling, Recurrent Neural Networks, Deep Learning, Machine Learning, Interpretability, NASDAQ Stockholm

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Contents

List of Abbreviations and Key Terms

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	1
1.2	Problem Formulation	2
1.3	Motivation	2
1.4	Objectives	3
1.5	Contributions of the Work	3
1.6	Scope and Limitations	4
1.7	Target Audience	4
1.8	Thesis Structure	4
2	Related Work	6
2.1	Review of Existing Research	6
2.1.1	Evidence for Predictive Power of Technical Indicators	6
2.1.2	Feature Selection in Machine Learning for Finance	8
2.1.3	Existing Classifications of Technical Indicators	9
2.1.4	Emerging Consensus on High-Level Indicator Families	11
2.1.5	Dominance of LSTM-Based Models	14
2.1.6	Interpretability in Machine Learning	15
2.2	Identified Gaps and Positioning of this Work	17
2.3	Summary	17
3	Methodology	19
3.1	Research Approach	19
3.2	Data Collection	24
3.2.1	Data Source & Scope	24
3.2.2	Data Variables	24
3.2.3	Data Retrieval Process	24
3.2.4	Inclusion / Exclusion Criteria	24
3.3	Data Analysis	25
3.3.1	Feature Engineering	25
3.3.2	Model Specification	25
3.3.3	Analysis Techniques	26
3.3.4	Feature Selection Logic	27
3.3.5	Evaluation Under the PDR Framework	27
3.4	Reliability and Validity	27
3.5	Ethical Considerations	28
3.6	Summary	28
4	Results and Analysis	29
4.1	Results	29
4.1.1	Preliminary Findings from Setup Exploration	29
4.1.2	Forward Selection Experiments	31
4.1.3	Stability Tests	34
4.1.4	Test-Set Evaluation	36
4.2	Analysis	42
4.2.1	General Analysis	42

4.2.2	Evaluation under PDR	44
5	Discussion	45
5.1	Revisiting Research Objectives	45
5.2	Insights from Experimental Results	46
5.3	Interpretability in Context	47
5.4	Comparison with Prior Work	47
5.5	Limitations	48
6	Conclusion and Future Work	50
6.1	Summary of Contributions	50
6.2	Practical and Theoretical Implications	50
6.3	Future Work	51
	References	52
A	Complete Visualization of SEB Class A Stock Data	58

List of Abbreviations and Key Terms

ABBR/Term	Definition
50/200 Crossover	SMA A trend-following breakout rule that compares a fast 50-day SMA to a slow 200-day SMA; signals arise when the short average crosses above or below the long average.
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average. A class of linear time-series models that combine autoregression, differencing, and moving averages to capture serial dependence in returns.
ARCH	Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity. A volatility model where the conditional variance depends on past squared residuals.
ATR	Average True Range. A volatility indicator measuring the average range between high and low (and gaps) over a rolling window.
BiLSTM	Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory network. An LSTM architecture that processes the input sequence forward and backward and concatenates both hidden representations.
Bollinger Bands	A volatility envelope constructed from a moving average and upper/lower bands at a fixed number of standard deviations, used to highlight unusually high or low price deviations from the mean.
Chaikin Oscillator	A volume-based oscillator that computes the difference between fast and slow EMAs of the Accumulation/Distribution (A/D) line, intended to capture short-term shifts in buying versus selling pressure.
Chart pattern	A recurring geometric shape in price charts (e.g., head-and-shoulders, flags) that traders interpret as signalling future price movements or trend reversals.
CMF	Chaikin Money Flow. A volume-based indicator that combines price and volume to approximate buying versus selling pressure over a window.
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network. A neural architecture that uses convolutional filters to extract local patterns; mainly used here as a contrasting sequential model in the literature.
CS-IS	Cross-Sectional In-Sample. Evaluation of predictions on stocks that <i>are</i> part of the training universe at a given time step
CS-OOS	Cross-Sectional Out-of-Sample. Evaluation of predictions on stocks that <i>are not</i> part of the training universe at a given time step.
DJIA	Dow Jones Industrial Average. A U.S. stock market index composed of 30 large, publicly traded companies; used in classic studies of technical trading rules.
DNN	Deep Neural Network. A neural network architecture with multiple hidden layers that learns hierarchical feature representations from data.
Domain-informed modeling	Modeling where domain knowledge (here, financial theory) constrains the feature space, rather than relying solely on unconstrained learning from raw inputs.

Donchian Channel	A price channel defined by the highest high and lowest low over a lookback window, used to identify breakouts above resistance or below support.
EMA	Exponential Moving Average. A moving average that assigns exponentially decaying weights to older prices, making it more responsive to recent movements than an SMA.
EMH	Efficient Market Hypothesis. The hypothesis that asset prices fully and instantaneously reflect available information, implying that persistent outperformance using publicly known signals is difficult or impossible.
Forward selection	A stepwise feature selection procedure that starts from an empty set and adds one feature at a time based on a performance criterion (e.g., out-of-sample R^2).
GARCH	Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity. A volatility model that extends ARCH by allowing both past squared residuals and past variances to enter the conditional variance.
GNN	Graph Neural Network. A neural architecture that operates on graph-structured data; here used as an example of more complex sequence or relation models in the literature.
HLC3	High–Low–Close Average. A price transform defined as $\frac{\text{High}+\text{Low}+\text{Close}}{3}$, often used as an input to indicators.
HWMA	Hull Weighted Moving Average. A moving average that combines weighted moving averages of different lengths to reduce lag while maintaining smoothness, aiming to track trend changes more responsively.
Ichimoku Cloud	A multi-component trend and support/resistance indicator that combines several shifted moving averages into a “cloud”, aiming to show trend direction, momentum, and key support/resistance zones in a single overlay.
KAMA	Kaufman Adaptive Moving Average. A moving average that adapts its smoothing factor based on price “efficiency”, aiming to be smooth in ranges and responsive in trends.
Keltner Channel	A volatility envelope built around an EMA, with upper and lower bands typically set at a multiple of the Average True Range (ATR), used to highlight breakouts beyond recent volatility.
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations. A post-hoc explanation method that fits simple surrogate models around individual predictions to approximate local behaviour of a black-box model.
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory network. A gated recurrent neural network architecture designed to capture long-range dependencies and mitigate vanishing gradients in sequence modeling.
MACD	Moving Average Convergence Divergence. A trend–momentum indicator based on the difference between two EMAs and a signal line.
MAE	Mean Absolute Error. A loss metric equal to the average absolute difference between predicted and actual values.

MFI	Money Flow Index. A volume-weighted momentum indicator that uses price and volume to detect overbought and oversold conditions.
ML	Machine Learning. Data-driven methods that learn patterns from historical data to make predictions or decisions.
Momentum Exhaustion Signals	Subgroup of momentum indicators designed to detect overbought or oversold conditions and potential reversal points (e.g., RSI, Stochastic Oscillator).
Momentum indicator	An indicator measuring the speed and strength of recent price changes, often implemented as bounded oscillators (e.g., RSI, ROC).
Momentum Persistence Signals	Subgroup of momentum indicators that track the continuation and strength of ongoing price moves rather than exhaustion (e.g., HLC3, RVI, Price ROC).
MSE	Mean Squared Error. A loss metric equal to the average squared difference between predicted and actual values.
NASDAQ	National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations. Here used to denote NASDAQ Stockholm, the exchange from which the equity data is drawn.
OBV	On-Balance Volume. A cumulative volume indicator that adds or subtracts the day's volume depending on whether price closed up or down, used to approximate buying versus selling pressure over time.
OHLCV	Open-High-Low-Close-Volume. A standard five-dimensional representation of a trading period, consisting of the opening price, highest and lowest traded prices, closing price, and traded volume for an asset over that interval.
PCA	Principal Component Analysis. A linear dimensionality-reduction technique that projects data onto orthogonal directions of maximum variance.
PDR	Predictive, Descriptive, and Relevant. An interpretability framework where methods are judged by predictive accuracy (P), descriptive accuracy (D), and relevance to human reasoning (R).
Price Distance	A dispersion indicator that measures the distance between price and a reference level (e.g., a moving average or prior close), capturing how far prices have moved away from a baseline.
Price ROC	Price Rate of Change. A momentum indicator measuring the percentage change in price over a specified lookback window, used to quantify how fast prices are rising or falling.
PVT	Price-Volume Trend. A cumulative volume-based indicator where volume is added or subtracted based on the sign of price changes.
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network. A neural architecture for sequence data that maintains a hidden state updated at each time step.
Rolling Std Dev	A volatility indicator defined as the rolling standard deviation of returns or prices over a fixed window, used as a simple dispersion measure.
RVI	Relative Vigor Index. An oscillator that compares the close relative to the trading range to quantify the "vigor" of a move.

RSI	Relative Strength Index. A bounded momentum oscillator that compares average gains to average losses over a window to identify overbought or oversold conditions.
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations. A post-hoc explanation method that attributes a model prediction to individual input features using Shapley values from cooperative game theory.
Sliding window	A data preparation scheme for time series where overlapping fixed-length subsequences (windows) are extracted to form supervised learning examples.
SMA	Simple Moving Average. The arithmetic mean of prices over a fixed lookback window.
Stochastic Oscillator	A bounded momentum oscillator that compares the current close to the recent high–low range over a lookback window, used to identify exhaustion in up- or down-moves.
Support and resistance	Price levels that have historically acted as floors (support) or ceilings (resistance) for price movements, often used as reference points in trading decisions.
SVM	Support Vector Machine. A margin-based learning algorithm; here referenced mainly through its regression variant (SVR) in financial forecasting.
SVR	Support Vector Regression. The regression version of SVM, which fits a function within an ε -insensitive tube while maximizing the margin.
SWMA	Smoothed Weighted Moving Average. A moving average that first applies weights to recent prices and then applies an additional smoothing step, producing a smoother trend estimate than a standard weighted moving average.
Technical indicator	A single-asset, price/volume-based signal computed deterministically from that asset's own OHLCV time series (e.g., moving averages, oscillators), designed to extract specific aspects of market behavior such as trend, momentum, volatility, or liquidity.
TEMA	Triple Exponential Moving Average. A moving average that combines single, double, and triple EMAs to reduce lag while preserving smoothness.
TFT	Temporal Fusion Transformer. A sequence model that combines recurrent encoders, multi-head attention, and gating mechanisms to handle multi-horizon time-series forecasting with static and time-varying covariates.
T-IS	Temporal In-Sample. Temporal splits within the training period used for validation or model selection.
T-OOS	Temporal Out-of-Sample. A held-out future period used to evaluate temporal generalization performance.
Trend Breakouts	Subgroup of trend indicators that focus on decisive moves through key levels or crossovers (e.g., 50/200 SMA Crossover, MACD, Ichimoku Cloud).
Trend Filters	Subgroup of trend indicators that smooth prices to extract the underlying direction of the market (e.g., SMA, TEMA, KAMA).
Trend indicator	An indicator designed to capture the direction and persistence of price movements over a horizon (e.g., moving averages, MACD).

Volatility Dispersion	Subgroup of volatility indicators that quantify raw variability of prices or returns (e.g., ATR, Rolling Std Dev, Price Distance).
Volatility Envelopes	Subgroup of volatility indicators that wrap prices in upper and lower bands or channels to highlight unusually high or low deviations (e.g., Bollinger Bands, Keltner Channel, Donchian Channel).
Volatility indicator	An indicator that quantifies the variability or dispersion of prices over time (e.g., ATR, Bollinger Bands).
Volume indicator	An indicator derived from trading volume and price to approximate buying and selling pressure (e.g., OBV, MFI, CMF).
Volume Cumulative Flows	Subgroup of volume indicators that cumulatively aggregate volume with a directional sign to approximate accumulation or distribution (e.g., OBV, PVT, CMF).
Volume Flow Oscillators	Subgroup of volume indicators that transform price–volume flows into oscillators to flag short-term shifts in buying and selling pressure (e.g., MFI, Volume ROC, Chaikin Oscillator).
Volume ROC	Volume Rate of Change. A momentum-style indicator applied to trading volume, measuring the percentage change in volume over a lookback window to capture accelerations or decelerations in trading activity.
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence. An umbrella term for methods and frameworks that make model predictions more understandable to humans.
XGBoost	Extreme Gradient Boosting. A tree-based ensemble method that uses gradient boosting; widely used as a strong baseline in tabular prediction tasks.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Capital markets exist to channel society’s savings toward builders and innovators, transforming idle wealth into corporate growth, infrastructure, and long-term financial security [1, 2]. The financial system carries out this role by mobilizing idle capital through banks and equity markets into enterprises, retirement funds, and other productive uses [3, 4]. In theory, this process should maximize collective prosperity by directing resources to their most productive use.

In practice, however, that allocation depends on accurately predicting returns—a task proven so difficult that, despite decades of research, individual investors and equity mutual funds consistently underperform the market on average [5, 6]. This pattern is explained by the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), first formalized by Eugene Fama in 1970 [7], which posits that all available information is already reflected in asset prices, leaving little room for systematic excess returns.

Fama classified market efficiency into three distinct forms—strong, semi-strong, and weak—based on which information set best represents market behavior. The weak form claims that past prices and volume data are already included in the current stock prices, rendering technical analysis obsolete. The semi-strong form, most supported by empirical evidence, argues that asset valuation captures all publicly available information; thus, neither technical nor fundamental analysis can systematically generate excess returns. The strong form asserts that the markets are perfectly efficient, with even insider information already incorporated; thus, no form of analysis provides a consistent advantage [7].

While still widely accepted, EMH has come under heavy scrutiny over the years. Grossman and Stiglitz [8] and Daniel et al. [9] argue that information asymmetries and investor psychology make perfect efficiency unattainable. Empirical anomalies—such as short-term momentum [10], long-term mean reversion, and overreaction [11]—demonstrate that prices are not fully efficient, creating pockets of predictability. To address these cracks, researchers turned to econometrics—statistical methods developed since the 1930s for analyzing economic relationships [12]—and adapted them to financial returns. Prominent approaches included Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) [13], Auto Regressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (ARCH) [14], and its Generalized variant—GARCH [15]. These models imposed statistical discipline on return forecasting, yet their reliance on linear assumptions left much of market complexity uncaptured, creating demand for more flexible methods that soon followed.

1988 brought the first application of machine learning in financial forecasting. Riding the wave of neural network revival enabled by backpropagation [16], White revisited earlier conceptual work on artificial neurons [17, 18] and built the first case study on IBM daily stock returns [19]. His three-layer neural network delivered substantially stronger predictive performance than linear autoregressions, establishing machine learning as a credible alternative to traditional econometrics in financial forecasting.

The 1990s saw the rise of Support Vector Machines (SVM) [20], which proved especially effective at handling high-dimensional inputs through kernel methods. Deep neural networks (DNN) gained prominence in the 2000s and 2010s by reducing the reliance on manual feature design that constrained SVMs through learning directly from raw inputs. Eventually, need for capturing long horizon sequential dependencies that DNNs struggled with led to the pivot toward recurrent architectures [21]. Among these, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [22] and their bidirectional extension (BiLSTM) [23] have since 2020 become central to financial forecasting [24].

Machine learning models now routinely outperform traditional econometrics in predictive accuracy, with recent works presenting robust empirical challenges to EMH [25]. Yet their opacity and limited theoretical anchoring in economics leave open the question of how, and why, these predictive gains arise — a tension that continues to shape contemporary financial research.

1.2 Problem Formulation

Despite nearly four decades of advances in predictive performance, machine learning research has made relatively little progress in interpretability. As Lipton argues, the field still tends to prioritize “the destination over the journey,” treating feature selection as a matter of performance optimization rather than a point of domain-informed decision-making. [26]

Most studies have traditionally relied on purely mathematical feature selection via wrapper, filter, and embedded methods. [27] While these approaches can improve predictive accuracy and offer insights into why certain inputs matter statistically, they typically score or select indicators independently or additively, ignoring a priori economic groupings and multivariate relationships that only emerge when features are considered jointly. [28] As a result, the structures uncovered by ML models are rarely retained as domain insight, limiting their contribution to empirical understanding of capital markets. [29]

In response to these concerns, much interpretability work has focused on post-hoc tools such as Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) [30] and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [31]. These methods are model-agnostic and widely applicable, but they leave the underlying feature space unchanged and do not, by themselves, embed domain knowledge into the model design.

Murdoch et al. advance the discourse by distinguishing interpretability during model construction (*model-based*) from interpretability after training (*post-hoc*) and reintroducing manual feature engineering, previously de-emphasized by end-to-end representation learning. The authors argue that descriptive accuracy of a model can be improved by constraining the feature space with the existing domain knowledge—an approach they term domain-informed modeling [32].

While domain-informed modeling has gained attention in broader interpretable ML research, it remains largely absent from financial time-series forecasting. A review of the literature reveals no prior integration of domain-driven technical indicator selection with ML-based stock forecasting. This study, therefore, asks:

Research Question Does constraining forward selection using a theory-informed technical-indicator taxonomy improve (a) predictive accuracy (R^2) and (b) interpretability under the PDR framework, when forecasting stock returns on NASDAQ Stockholm?

1.3 Motivation

Decades of econometric and machine-learning research have repeatedly highlighted a small set of technical indicators—such as moving averages, on-balance volume, momentum oscillators, and volatility bands—that recur as useful predictors in equity-forecasting models. At the same time, both academic surveys and practitioner guides organize these tools into a handful of functional families with characteristic behaviours (e.g., trend, momentum, volatility, volume, chart-based), but this structure is rarely used as

an explicit design constraint when constructing feature sets for machine-learning models. Most empirical evidence also comes from large markets such as the U.S. and China, while smaller but mature exchanges, such as NASDAQ Stockholm, remain comparatively under-studied. This thesis therefore addresses both a methodological gap—domain-informed, interpretable feature selection for ML-based stock-return forecasting—and an empirical gap—assessing the behaviour of these indicators in a mid-sized European market.

1.4 Objectives

This thesis is structured around six research objectives, summarized in Table 1.2. Objectives O1—O3 define the core experimental setup: they specify how domain knowledge is encoded into a taxonomy of technical indicators, how this taxonomy is integrated into the feature-selection procedure, and how predictive performance is evaluated on NASDAQ Stockholm equities under two hold-out regimes. Objectives O4—O6 extend this core by focusing on interpretability and robustness under the PDR framework: they frame a qualitative assessment of family-level contribution patterns and practitioner usefulness at the 10-day horizon, and examine how normalization choices and differences between cross-sectional and temporal hold-out schemes affect performance. In this sense, O4 speaks to the descriptive and relevant aspects of PDR, while O5 and O6 function as robustness checks on the stability and generalizability of the main findings.

Table 1.2: Research objectives

Code	Objective
O1	Construct and justify a domain-informed taxonomy for a widely used set of 24 technical indicators, grounded in financial economics and technical-analysis literature, and operationalize it as a design constraint for feature selection in stock-return forecasting.
O2	Implement taxonomy-constrained forward selection on a set of 24 technical indicators at both indicator and family levels.
O3	Quantify out-of-sample performance (R^2 , MSE) of the BiLSTM forecasting models on NASDAQ Stockholm equities (2015–2025) under two hold-out regimes.
O4	Assess interpretability qualitatively by (i) describing family-level contribution patterns during forward selection and (ii) discussing practitioner usefulness at the 10-day horizon.
O5	Investigate the role of normalization strategies (per-universe, per-stock, per-window) in shaping forecasting outcomes.
O6	Examine generalization across both cross-sectional and temporal hold-out schemes.

1.5 Contributions of the Work

- **Conceptual:** This work formalizes and documents a hierarchical, domain-informed taxonomy for a commonly used set of 24 technical indicators, synthesizing families that often recur in prior econometric, technical-analysis, and ML studies.
- **Technical:** This work delivers a reproducible BiLSTM training, evaluation, and visualization suite—complete with hold-out and walk-forward validation and performance testing.

- **Empirical:** This thesis represents one of the earliest studies of taxonomy-driven indicator selection on the Swedish equity market (NASDAQ Stockholm, 2015–2025), identifying which indicator classes and specific features yield the greatest forecasting accuracy improvements.

1.6 Scope and Limitations

- **Market scope:** Equities with a minimum history of 1000 trading days on NASDAQ Stockholm between 2015 and 2025 and no more than 5% of non-trading days. Results may not generalize to other exchanges or asset classes.
- **Feature domain:** Only 24 trend, volume, volatility, and momentum technical indicators are considered. Macroeconomic, market strength, and sentiment indicators, alongside charting and alternative data sources (e.g., news text) are excluded.
- **Model class:** Experiments focus exclusively on the BiLSTM architecture. Other models (e.g., ARIMA, GARCH, transformers) are outside the present scope.
- **Evaluation:** Test on daily (stride-1) rolling windows based on a combined temporal and cross-sectional hold-out split (90/10), ensuring robustness across both time and stocks. No transaction-cost simulation or live trading is performed.
- **Interpretability:** The focus is on group-level feature contributions rather than model-internal explainability (e.g., SHAP, LIME), which is reserved for future work.

1.7 Target Audience

- **Academic researchers** in machine learning, time-series forecasting, and financial econometrics, seeking domain-informed feature selection methods.
- **Quantitative finance practitioners** and **fintech engineers** interested in interpretable forecasting.
- **Financial analysts** and **portfolio managers** interested in identifying which classes of technical indicators most strongly drive predictive performance.

1.8 Thesis Structure

The structure of this thesis reflects the progression of the project, from identifying the problem to presenting results and drawing conclusions.

- **Section 1** introduces the topic, defines the research problem, outlines the project objectives, and explains the scope and limitations.
- **Section 2** reviews relevant literature in the areas of technical analysis, stock forecasting, time series models, and feature selection, providing context and highlighting gaps that this thesis addresses.
- **Section 3** describes the overall methodology, including the dataset, feature taxonomy, chosen models, and evaluation strategy.

- **Section 4** presents the experimental results from BiLSTM models trained on different feature groups, with a focus on MSE, MAE and R^2 metrics.
- **Section 5** offers a discussion of the results, considers their implications, and reflects on the strengths and limitations of the approach taken.
- **Section 6** concludes the thesis with a summary of findings and suggestions for future work.

2 Related Work

This section first reviews prior research on the predictive capacity of technical indicators, feature selection approaches, indicator groupings, relevant machine-learning models, and interpretability (Section 2.1), then identifies gaps and positions the present contribution (Section 2.2), and finally summarizes the key takeaways (Section 2.3).

2.1 Review of Existing Research

2.1.1 Evidence for Predictive Power of Technical Indicators

Existing empirical work on technical analysis offers a mixed but informative picture of whether technical indicators can forecast equity returns. Early studies reported statistically significant profits from simple trend-following and breakout rules, while later surveys and robustness checks showed that such profitability often clusters in specific markets and subperiods and can disappear once data-snooping and transaction costs are accounted for. This subsection reviews these strands of evidence, including recent machine-learning studies, to clarify how strong, stable, and model-dependent the predictive content of technical indicators appears to be in practice.

Early Evidence from Simple Technical Rules. The earliest large-scale tests of technical rules date to Brock et al. [33]. They applied 16 variants of moving-average rules and 10 variants of trading-range breakouts to over 90 years of Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJIA) data. Every buy-sell spread generated by these 26 rules remained significantly positive under four alternative null models—random walk, AR(1), GARCH-in-mean (GARCH-M, an extension of ARCH-M [34] with a GARCH [15] volatility specification), and Exponential GARCH (EGARCH) [35]. No single variant dominated; rather, the consistent profitability across both moving-average and breakout rules provided early and influential evidence that simple technical strategies captured patterns in stock returns unexplained by standard models.

In later research, Neely et al. [36] analyzed 14 variants of moving averages, momentum, and on-balance volume for forecasting the U.S. equity risk premium using one-sided wild-bootstrap p -values [37, 38, 39]. They found that 13 of 14 rules reject the null hypothesis of no predictability in-sample, while all 14 deliver positive out-of-sample R^2 performance; 6 of these results are statistically significant under the Clark–West adjustment [40].

Survey Evidence and Methodological Caveats. While earlier studies tested specific indicators or trading rules, Park and Irwin’s [41] comprehensive survey looked at 137 empirical studies published between 1960 and 2004, including 95 "modern" studies conducted after 1988. Among these modern studies, 56 (59%) report net trading profits after transaction costs, 20 (21%) report losses, and 19 (20%) produce mixed outcomes. The survey shows that evidence of profitability is not uniform but tends to concentrate in particular markets and subperiods. Indicators most frequently associated with positive results include simple moving averages, filter rules, momentum oscillators, OBV, and chart-patterns. At the same time, Park and Irwin caution that many studies suffer from methodological weaknesses—most notably data snooping, ex post rule selection, and insufficient treatment of risk and costs—which limit the conclusiveness of the evidence. [41]

Robustness Checks on Market-Wide Signals. While Park and Irwin’s survey suggested that profitability evidence tends to cluster around certain indicators and markets, Fang et al. [42] adopt a more systematic stress test of those claims. They examine 93 widely cited market indicators—ranging from sentiment measures such as short interest and option volumes to breadth measures like the advance–decline line and counts of new highs and lows—subjecting them to OLS regressions, split-sample stability tests, rolling windows, and adjustments for risk and transaction costs. At first glance, 30 indicators appear statistically significant at the conventional 10% level, but only 10 survive split-sample checks, and none yield positive risk-adjusted returns. Even long-standing favorites among practitioners, such as advances/declines and new highs/lows, fail robustness tests. Fang and colleagues thus conclude that once data-snooping, sample instability, and costs are properly accounted for, the predictive power of technical market indicators largely vanishes. [42]

Recent ML Evidence on Indicator Importance. In a more recent approach, Mostafavi and Hooman [43] turned to machine learning to identify the most influential technical indicators for forecasting the S&P500 index. Using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [44, 45], they reduced an initial set of 88 commonly used indicators to 35 components representing 95% of the variance, which were then evaluated using Support Vector Regression (SVR) [46], Random Forest [47], XGBoost [48], and LSTM models.

Their results highlight both model-specific preferences and cross-model consistencies. For example, SVR favored the Money Flow Index (MFI), High-Low-Close Average (HLC3) and Triple Exponential Moving Average (TEMA), Random Forest emphasized On-Balance Volume (OBV), HLC3, and Smoothed Weighted Moving Average (SWMA), XGBoost mostly prioritized Ichimoku Cloud, Hull Weighted Moving Average (HWMA), and OBV, while LSTM consistently ranked HLC3, OBV, TEMA and Bollinger Bands among its top features. Only three indicators—HLC3, OBV and TEMA—emerged as universally significant across all 4 models. A secondary group of indicators, including Kaufman’s Adaptive Moving Average (KAMA), Average True Range (ATR), Relative Vigor Index (RVI), Price-Volume Trend (PVT), and Price Distance also proved influential in at least one model, though their importance was less consistent than the model-specific leaders and far from the universal significance of the core trio.

Summary. Taken together, these studies paint a nuanced view of technical indicators as sources of predictability. Early rule-based tests and surveys documented statistically significant profits and recurring roles for trend, momentum, and volume-related signals, but robustness checks on market-wide indicators suggest that much of this profitability is fragile once data-snooping, instability, and costs are addressed. At the same time, recent machine-learning studies recover a small set of recurrently important signals and non-trivial out-of-sample performance. Technical indicators are therefore not assumed to deliver robust excess returns on their own, but are treated as potentially weak, model- and regime-dependent predictors whose structure and grouping warrant careful, interpretable organization. In this thesis, that role is made explicit by focusing on a widely used set of 24 single-asset indicators and organizing them into a domain-informed taxonomy over four economic families, which then serves as the backbone for the feature-selection experiments.

2.1.2 Feature Selection in Machine Learning for Finance

Feature selection plays a central role in stock-forecasting models that rely on large sets of technical indicators and related inputs. Because these feature sets often contain many overlapping transformations of the same OHLCV series, they are typically redundant and exhibit non-linear dependencies. This subsection reviews which inputs prior work has used and how classical feature selection methods have been applied in machine-learning models for finance.

Prevalence of Technical Inputs and the Need for Feature Selection. Systematic reviews by Nti et al. [49] and Kumbure et al. [24] provide quantitative overviews of technical rules and machine-learning inputs in finance research. Nti et al. reviewed 122 machine-learning-based stock-prediction studies published between 2007 and 2018, finding that 66% relied solely on technical indicators (most commonly SMA, EMA, MACD, RSI, and OBV), 23% used fundamental inputs, and 11% combined both. [49] Kumbure et al. examined 138 journal articles published between 2000 and 2019, cataloging 2,173 unique input variables—62.0% technical indicators, 12.8% macro-economic variables, 7.2% fundamental indicators, and the remainder were "other" types. [24] These findings underscore that technical analysis is the most popular approach among the reviewed studies.

Given the sheer volume of over 2000 distinct inputs, many being permutations of same technical indicators, data in financial time series is often riddled with nonlinear dependencies. This necessitates robust feature selection mechanisms capable of weeding out noise without destroying multidimensional relationships. Existing feature selection mechanisms for ML research generally and financial time series specifically fall broadly into 3 categories: filter, wrapper, and embedded methods. [28]

Wrapper Methods. These methods treat feature selection as a search problem wrapped around the modeling algorithm. By iteratively adding or removing one indicator at a time (forward/backward selection) or by recursively eliminating the least important features, wrappers directly optimize the chosen validation metric (e.g. MAE, MSE, R^2 , depending on task). Because the model is retrained for each candidate subset, wrappers implicitly capture interactions to the extent the model can learn them, but offer no explicit representation of those dependencies. This comes at a high computational cost, risk of overfitting on small samples, and no economic interpretability [28].

Filter Methods. Filter methods sit entirely outside the modeling loop, scoring each indicator on simple statistical criteria such as Pearson correlation for linear relevance, mutual information for nonlinear relevance, or univariate p-values. This makes them extremely fast, scalable to hundreds or thousands of variables, and highly interpretable. However, by treating each indicator in isolation, filters can miss pairs and higher-order combinations that matter only when considered jointly. They may also inflate false positives when many indicators are screened simultaneously unless combined with proper cross-validation or false discovery controls. Like wrappers, they rely purely on statistical dependencies, ignoring domain knowledge and offering limited insight into financial context [28].

Embedded Methods. Embedded approaches integrate selection into the learning algorithm. Penalized linear models (Lasso, Elastic Net) shrink many coefficients to zero,

controlling variance under collinearity. Tree-based models (e.g., Random Forests, Gradient Boosted Trees) provide embedded selection by prioritizing features that most reduce impurity [28]. These methods strike a balance: they account for some feature interdependencies via the penalty or split criteria, and the cost scales linearly with the number of features. But they still focus on additive, linear effects unless extended (e.g., grouped lasso or explicit interaction terms), and they arbitrarily distribute importance among highly correlated indicators—potentially discarding entire families of related signals.

Lack of Domain Knowledge in Standard Feature Selection. Despite these advantages, none of the classical selection methods embed financial theory into feature selection. They can reduce dimensionality and improve predictive performance, but they: (a) provide limited financial interpretability, (b) disregard domain knowledge in their selection processes, and (c) may miss higher-order interdependencies of technical indicators.

Summary. Empirical reviews show that machine-learning models for stock forecasting typically rely on large collections of technical indicators and related inputs, leading to high-dimensional, redundant feature spaces. Classical filter, wrapper, and embedded methods provide generic tools to reduce this dimensionality, but treat indicators as flat variables rather than structured financial signals and embed little domain knowledge in their selection criteria.

2.1.3 Existing Classifications of Technical Indicators

Existing work on stock market forecasting offers several ways of grouping technical tools, ranging from broad input taxonomies to more focused classifications of specific trading rules or market-wide indicators. Before proposing a taxonomy tailored to this study, it is therefore important to examine how prior studies have organized technical indicators and to what extent those groupings align with the requirements of an interpretability-focused, single-asset forecasting setup. This subsection reviews the main existing classifications and clarifies why none of them can be adopted directly as an a priori hierarchy over the technical indicators used in this study.

Usage-Driven Input Taxonomy. Bustos and Pomares-Quimbaya [50] propose a taxonomy of input variables that distinguishes technical indicators, stock price series, macroeconomic and other ‘fundamental’ time series, and various forms of unstructured text (e.g. news, blogs, social networks), based on how these inputs are used in the surveyed forecasting models. The resulting taxonomy is therefore descriptive and usage-driven: it summarizes which inputs prior studies have relied on most often rather than imposing an a priori, theory-based partition of the indicator space. [50]

Within the technical category, Bustos and Pomares-Quimbaya distinguish two main types of indicators—trend indicators and oscillators—where the former focus on the direction of the price movement and the latter are used to identify potential turning points in the time series [50]. This provides a useful coarse functional split, but it is not developed into a more detailed hierarchy of individual indicators.

Instead, commonly used tools such as moving averages, MACD, RSI, and stochastic oscillators are presented as examples rather than being systematically organized into families that would exhaustively cover the broader universe of single-asset technical indicators. In particular, the taxonomy does not attempt to classify many widely used price-

and volume-based indicators such as Ichimoku Cloud, Kaufman Adaptive Moving Average (KAMA), or Chaikin Money Flow (CMF), all of which belong to the 24-indicator set used in this thesis.

As a result, while their framework is valuable as a high-level overview of input types and a coarse trend–oscillator dichotomy, it does not provide the more granular, domain-informed hierarchy over individual technical indicators that is required for the interpretability-focused design goal of this study.

Market-Level Technical Indicator Taxonomy. Fang et al. provide a more structured classification, but in a different segment of technical analysis. Their study examines 93 technical *market* indicators drawn from Global Financial Data, including aggregate option volumes, short interest ratios, volatility indices, advance–decline statistics, and counts of new highs and lows. [42]

These series are constructed from market-wide data and used to predict broad index returns, not individual stocks. Fang and colleagues group them into two overarching classes—*market sentiment* and *market strength*—and further subdivide them into 14 sub-groups based on the type of raw information employed (e.g., option-market activity, survey-based sentiment, breadth measures). This design is well suited to their objective of organizing market-level indicators, but it does not aim to cover the broader universe of single-asset technical indicators. Additionally, classical price- and volume-based tools such as Ichimoku Cloud, Kaufman Adaptive Moving Average (KAMA), or Chaikin Money Flow (CMF)—fall outside the scope of their taxonomy. As a result, while Fang et al.’s framework is informative about how market-wide indicators can be grouped, it does not offer an exhaustive or directly reusable family structure for classifying the full set of OHLCV-derived single-asset technical indicators considered in this study.

Empirical Groupings Without a Formal Taxonomy. Beyond these explicit survey-based classifications, several high-impact empirical studies and reviews implicitly organize technical rules or indicators into recurring families without proposing a formal taxonomy.

Brock et al. [33] concentrate on a small set of moving-average and trading-range breakout rules as representative systems and study their profitability on the Dow Jones Industrial Average, but do not attempt to classify the broader indicator space. Park and Irwin [41] survey the profitability of technical trading rules across markets and group them into categories such as filter rules, moving averages, channels, and momentum oscillators; these categories are defined at the level of trading systems and research traditions rather than as an exhaustive hierarchy over individual single-asset indicators.

Similarly, factor- and forecasting-oriented contributions such as Jegadeesh and Titman [10], Carhart [6], and Neely et al. [36] highlight specific momentum, moving-average, and volume-related signals as predictors, but treat them as lists of useful tools rather than elements of a unified classification scheme.

Collectively, these works reinforce the existence of recurring functional groupings in practice, yet they stop short of providing an explicit, comprehensive taxonomy over a fixed set of technical indicators that could be used as an a priori design constraint for interpretability-focused feature selection in this thesis.

Summary. Taken together, these contributions provide valuable structure at different levels: broad input-type taxonomies, classifications of market-wide indicators, and recurring families of trading rules and signals. However, they either operate at a different

level of aggregation (market indices rather than single stocks), offer only coarse or usage-driven splits within technical indicators, or list representative signals without building an explicit, exhaustive hierarchy over a fixed indicator set. For the purposes of this study, which requires a domain-informed grouping of single-asset technical indicators that can be used as an a priori design constraint in model construction, these existing classifications are therefore informative but not directly reusable. The next subsection synthesizes the recurring families identified here into a working first-layer grouping that will serve as the foundation for the proposed taxonomy.

2.1.4 Emerging Consensus on High-Level Indicator Families

The classifications reviewed in Section 2.1.3 show that prior work provides structure at various levels, but none offers a directly reusable hierarchy over the single-asset technical indicators considered in this study. At the same time, both academic studies and practitioner guides repeatedly refer to a small set of recurring functional families when discussing technical tools. This subsection summarizes that pattern and argues that, at a high level, there is an emerging, yet not fully established, consensus on a handful of core indicator families that can be operationalized as the first layer of a working taxonomy.

Evidence of recurring families. Table 2.3 reports a set of widely cited academic references and major practitioner sources from the 1990s to the 2020s that discuss technical indicators or trading rules in grouped form. For each source, the table records whether it explicitly names any of the high-level families listed in the column headings as category labels when organizing technical tools, alongside the publication year, source type (academic or practitioner), and an approximate citation count as a proxy for impact.

Table 2.3: Representative sources referencing high-level indicator families.

Year	Reference	Source	Citations	Trend	Mom.	Volat.	Vol.	S/R
1992	Brock et al. [33]	Acad.	≈ 3 700+	✓				✓
1993	Jegadeesh and Titman [10]	Acad.	≈ 17 400+		✓			
1997	Carhart [6]	Acad.	≈ 25 500+		✓			
2000	Lo et al. [51]	Acad.	≈ 2 000+	✓				✓
2001	Achelis [52]	Pract.	≈ 1 100+	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2007	Park and Irwin [41]	Acad.	≈ 1 000+	✓	✓		✓	
2014	Neely et al. [36]	Acad.	≈ 1 200+	✓	✓		✓	
2014	Fang et al. [42]	Acad.	≈ 70+			✓	✓	
2020	Bustos and Pomares-Quimbaya [50]	Acad.	≈ 450+	✓	✓			
2020s	Songer, Kirkpatrick / Fidelity [53, 54]	Pract.	n/a	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2020s	Rathburn / Investopedia [55]	Pract.	n/a	✓	✓		✓	

Table 2.3: Representative sources referencing high-level indicator families (continued).

Year	Reference	Source	Citations	Trend	Mom.	Volat.	Vol.	S/R
2025	Mostafavi and Hooman [43]	Acad.	≈ 10+	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Despite differences in market, horizon, and research focus—from rule-profitability tests and factor models to forecasting surveys and educational material—the same small set of families is repeatedly used to structure the discussion, both in the academic literature and in industry texts. Table 2.3 is illustrative rather than exhaustive, but the pattern it shows is unlikely to be accidental. Evidence for volatility as a named family is more recent and is concentrated in post-2000 practitioner and survey sources (e.g. Achelis [52], Fang et al. [42], Mostafavi and Hooman [43], and practitioner guides such as Songer and Kirkpatrick / Fidelity [53, 54]), reflecting the growing prominence of volatility-based tools in modern practice. Support and resistance, often operationalized through chart patterns or trading-range rules, likewise appear less frequently as an explicit category label, but play a consistent conceptual role in both academic studies and practitioner texts.

Taken together, these dimensions line up with basic questions about the price and volume process: whether prices exhibit a persistent direction (trend), how quickly and how far they move away from a reference level (momentum), how large and clustered the price fluctuations are (volatility), how intensively the asset is traded and by whom (volume), and around which price levels or geometric formations market participants appear to anchor (support and resistance). Because these dimensions are intuitive, tied to long-standing narratives in technical analysis, and empirically relevant for both trading-rule performance and asset-pricing studies, it is natural to treat the associated family labels as a convenient, literature-aligned top-level grouping for single-asset OHLCV-derived technical indicators, while not claiming them to be definitive or exhaustive.

Position relative to existing taxonomies. Compared to the broad, usage-driven input taxonomy proposed by Bustos and Pomares-Quimbaya [50], the high-level families used here are defined a priori at the level of single-asset technical indicators and are anchored in long-standing economic interpretations of the information each family is intended to capture, rather than being derived ex post from the frequency of appearances in prior studies. Relative to the market-level classification proposed by Fang et al. [42], the grouping focuses specifically on OHLCV-based transforms for individual assets and supplies a structured categorization for single-asset technical indicators, whereas Fang et al. classify aggregate market signals instead. On this basis, the remainder of this subsection summarizes the economic roles that the literature commonly associates with each of the main families.

Trend indicators. Trend indicators are designed to identify the prevailing direction and regime of prices over different horizons, typically by smoothing the underlying series or detecting breakouts from recent ranges. Classic examples include moving-average and trading-range rules, which are explicitly analysed as trend-following systems in empirical studies such as Brock et al. [33], Lo et al. [51], and Park and Irwin [41]. Surveys of technical inputs in forecasting models similarly list moving averages and related filters under

trend-type indicators, reinforcing the interpretation of this family as capturing directional persistence rather than short-term oscillations. [49, 50]

Momentum indicators. Momentum indicators focus on the speed, persistence, and potential reversal of price movements relative to a reference level, often operationalized via oscillators or rate-of-change measures around a baseline. In cross-sectional asset-pricing work, Carhart [6] and Jegadeesh and Titman [10] treat momentum as a distinct return pattern and factor, separate from level and volatility. In the technical-analysis literature, tools such as RSI, stochastic oscillators, and price rate-of-change are routinely grouped together as momentum or overbought/oversold indicators, both in empirical surveys and practitioner guides. [41, 49, 50]

Volatility indicators. Volatility indicators are intended to quantify the amplitude and clustering of price fluctuations, highlighting transitions between calm and turbulent regimes rather than the direction of movement. Typical examples include average true range (ATR), rolling standard deviations, and volatility bands such as Bollinger Bands, which are used as separate inputs in forecasting models [43]. Reviews of technical tools and market indicators similarly treat volatility-related measures as a distinct group, reflecting their role in signalling time-varying risk rather than trend or momentum per se. [42, 49]

Volume indicators. Volume indicators use trading activity to proxy for participation, liquidity, and the strength of buying or selling pressure, often by combining price changes with volume to infer accumulation or distribution. Empirical work and surveys distinguish volume-based rules and indicators—such as on-balance volume, Accumulation/Distribution, and related flow measures—from purely price-based trend and momentum rules. [36, 41] Practitioner and review articles likewise discuss volume indicators as a separate family that confirms or contradicts price movements, emphasising their informational role about how many market participants are supporting a given move. [49, 50]

Chart patterns and support/resistance. Chart-pattern and support/resistance tools form a fifth family in the broader technical-analysis tradition. Rather than producing scalar transforms of prices and volumes at each time step, they encode geometric features of the price path—such as trendlines, ranges, and formations like head-and-shoulders or double tops—and emphasize levels where supply and demand appear to rebalance. Academic work such as Lo et al. [51] and practitioner texts [52, 53, 56] treat these patterns and levels as distinct from indicator-based filters and oscillators, often relying on dedicated pattern-recognition rules or visual inspection. As a result, chart patterns are conceptually grouped together with support and resistance levels as a separate family of tools that complements, rather than overlaps with, the four indicator-based families above.

Summary. Evidence from academic studies and practitioner frameworks shows that technical tools are repeatedly organized into a small set of high-level families: trend, momentum, volatility, volume, and chart patterns/support–resistance. The economic roles of these families align with basic dimensions of the price and volume process—direction, speed, variability, participation, and key levels—rather than with ad hoc groupings. Taken together, this implicit, literature-backed grouping provides the conceptual backbone for the high-level groupings of the single-asset OHLCV-derived technical indicators.

2.1.5 Dominance of LSTM-Based Models

Recurrent neural networks have become one of the most widely used classes of models for stock-return prediction. In particular, LSTM and BiLSTM architectures are now widely used as standard sequential baselines in daily equity forecasting, replacing earlier static models such as SVR, SVM, tree ensembles, and shallow feed-forward networks. This subsection outlines the progression from static to recurrent models, summarizes the LSTM and BiLSTM mechanisms relevant for this study, and situates them among other recent sequential architectures proposed in financial applications.

From Static Models to Gated Recurrent Architectures. Early applications of machine learning to financial time series primarily relied on static models such as SVR, SVM, tree ensembles (e.g., Random Forest, XGBoost), and shallow feed-forward neural networks. [24, 49] These architectures operate on fixed-size feature vectors and treat each observation as conditionally independent, which allows the inclusion of lagged returns or indicators but does not model temporal dependencies explicitly. As a result, such models are limited in their ability to capture long-range interactions and regime shifts that unfold over multiple days or weeks in asset prices.

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) extend feed-forward architectures to sequential data by maintaining a hidden state that is updated at each time step based on the previous state and the current input. [21] In practice, conventional RNNs are difficult to train on longer sequences due to vanishing and exploding gradients, which makes it hard to learn dependencies that span more than a few time steps. [57] Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks address this limitation by introducing an explicit memory cell and a set of gating mechanisms that regulate how information is added to, removed from, and exposed from this memory. [22]

LSTM Gating and Memory Mechanics. An LSTM cell maintains a cell state c_t and a hidden state h_t at each time step t . Three gates, implemented as sigmoid-activated linear transformations, control the update of these states. Given an input vector x_t and the previous hidden state h_{t-1} , the forget gate f_t , input gate i_t , output gate o_t , and candidate cell update \tilde{c}_t are computed as in Eq. (1), following the formulation of Gers et al. [58].

$$\begin{aligned} f_t &= \sigma(W_f x_t + U_f h_{t-1} + b_f), \\ i_t &= \sigma(W_i x_t + U_i h_{t-1} + b_i), \\ o_t &= \sigma(W_o x_t + U_o h_{t-1} + b_o), \\ \tilde{c}_t &= \tanh(W_c x_t + U_c h_{t-1} + b_c), \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where W ., U ., and b denote learned weight matrices and bias vectors. The cell and hidden states are then updated according to Eq. (2):

$$\begin{aligned} c_t &= f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{c}_t, \\ h_t &= o_t \odot \tanh(c_t), \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where \odot denotes the element-wise (Hadamard) product.

The forget gate f_t controls which information from the previous cell state is retained, the input gate i_t and candidate state \tilde{c}_t determine what new information is written, and the output gate o_t selects which parts of the updated cell state are exposed to the next layer. Taken together, mechanisms described in Eqs. (1) and (2) allow LSTMs to preserve relevant temporal patterns over longer horizons while filtering out noise. [22, 58]

Bidirectional LSTM Architectures. Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) architectures extend this mechanism by processing the input sequence in both temporal directions. A forward LSTM reads the sequence from the earliest to the latest time step, producing hidden states \vec{h}_t , while a backward LSTM reads the same sequence in reverse, producing hidden states \overleftarrow{h}_t . For each time step t , the two representations are typically concatenated as in Eq. (3) to form a context-aware vector

$$h_t = [\vec{h}_t; \overleftarrow{h}_t], \quad (3)$$

which embeds information from both past and future positions within the input window. In fixed-length sliding windows, BiLSTMs can therefore exploit dependencies that depend on the relative position of observations within the window rather than only on past context. [23, 59]

Empirical Adoption in Financial Forecasting. In recent studies, Mostafavi and Hooman found LSTM models to outperform SVR, XGBoost, and Random Forest in stock index prediction, reinforcing the view that sequential architectures capture latent temporal dependencies better than static alternatives. [43] Survey studies report a significant increase in neural network-based approaches to stock market prediction from 2017 onward, with DNN architectures—in particular RNN and LSTM-style models—appearing alongside more traditional SVM and tree-based methods. [24, 49, 60] Recent work has introduced Transformer-based architectures such as Informer [61] and Temporal Fusion Transformers (TFT) [62] for long-horizon time-series forecasting, and graph neural networks have been explored for modeling cross-sectional structure in multi-asset settings [60]. However, empirical studies on daily equity returns still rely predominantly on LSTM-type networks as strong baselines, and newer Transformer and Graph Neural Networks (GNN) models remain comparatively less established in this domain. [24, 43, 60]

Summary. Overall, the progression from static models to gated recurrent architectures, together with the bidirectional extension and recent empirical results in stock prediction, has positioned LSTM-based networks as natural sequential baselines for daily equity forecasting. Empirical studies continue to report strong performance for LSTMs relative to static alternatives, while more complex architectures such as Transformers and graph neural networks remain less established in this specific domain.

2.1.6 Interpretability in Machine Learning

Interpretability has become a central concern as increasingly complex machine-learning models are deployed in high-stakes decision-making. In finance, as in medicine or criminal justice, purely predictive performance is often insufficient: practitioners also need to understand how models use their inputs and whether the patterns they exploit are trustworthy and aligned with domain knowledge. This subsection reviews conceptual and technical perspectives on interpretability, focusing on Lipton’s taxonomy and the Predictive–Descriptive–Relevant (PDR) framework introduced by Murdoch et al.

Risks of Black-Box Models and Benefits of Interpretability. The interpretability question has long been a problem in the field of Artificial Intelligence. There is both no consensus on the definition of interpretability in the scientific community and no comprehensive set of tools to fully unwrap and explain the complex patterns uncovered by different machine learning models. [26]

Traditionally, machine learning research has been concerned with outcomes more than with the findings, focusing on maximizing predictive accuracy at all costs. Whilst highly practical, this approach has been scrutinized due to its high potential for damage in high-stakes fields, such as medicine, criminal justice and financial decision making. For example, Caruana et al. [63] demonstrated that a model predicting pneumonia mortality risk mistakenly learned that patients with asthma had a lower risk of death. The reason behind such a prediction was that asthmatics historically received more aggressive treatment. If left uninterpreted, the model could have recommended less aggressive care with potentially fatal consequences. [63]

Lack of interpretability is also a missed opportunity at uncovering underlying patterns in the research domain. Lipton argues that interpretability can engender trust between human decision-makers and algorithmic systems, provide clues about possible causal structure, ensure robustness when training and deployment environments diverge, offer useful auxiliary information to human experts, and to assess fairness and ethical compliance. In this sense, interpretability is not a monolithic concept but a collection of objectives that vary depending on context. [26]

Transparency and Post-Hoc Explanations. On the technical level, Lipton distinguishes two broad approaches. The first is transparency, which can mean simulatability (the entire model is simple enough for a human to grasp at once), decomposability (each component—inputs, parameters, calculations—admits an intuitive explanation), or algorithmic transparency (the training procedure is provably well-behaved). The second is post-hoc interpretability, which extracts explanations after training, through natural-language rationales, saliency maps, visualization of learned representations, or case-based analogies. While transparency aims to expose mechanisms, post-hoc explanations instead provide useful signals to stakeholders even if they do not reveal the model’s inner workings. [26]

Predictive–Descriptive–Relevant (PDR) Framework. Building on this view, Murdoch et al. formalize a unified Predictive–Descriptive–Relevant (PDR) framework with three desiderata—predictive accuracy, descriptive accuracy, and relevancy—and categorize interpretability methods into two stages: *model-based* during the modeling stage and *post-hoc* after training. [32]

A unique contribution of the PDR framework is that it specifies criteria for measuring interpretability across these three desiderata. Predictive accuracy is evaluated on out-of-sample performance. Descriptive accuracy is operationalized through sparsity (a small number of non-zero parameters), stability of selected features under small data perturbations, and structural constraints that enable simulatability or modular, component-wise interpretation. Relevancy is assessed qualitatively via alignment with domain knowledge and the ability of explanations to support the intended audience’s decisions. [32]

Model-based approaches typically trade some predictive accuracy for higher descriptive accuracy, whereas post-hoc methods leave predictive accuracy unchanged while extracting insights from a trained model; relevancy anchors both to the audience and task. Murdoch et al. also note that improved feature engineering can increase predictive accuracy, and that incorporating domain knowledge in the form of sparsity can raise both predictive accuracy and relevancy. [32]

Summary. Interpretability is not a single property but a context-dependent collection of goals, ranging from avoiding harmful decisions to uncovering useful domain structure and

supporting human judgement. The PDR framework makes these goals explicit by separating predictive accuracy from descriptive accuracy and relevancy, and by distinguishing model-based design choices from post-hoc explanation tools. In this study, interpretability is evaluated through this lens: models are expected not only to achieve reasonable predictive accuracy, but also to provide stable, sparse, and domain-aligned accounts of how technical indicators contribute to stock-return forecasts.

2.2 Identified Gaps and Positioning of this Work

The literature review highlights three persistent gaps that this thesis addresses:

1. **Lack of functional grouping.** Technical indicators are treated as isolated variables, not grouped by economic function. Even with feature selection, indicators are ranked or dropped individually, ignoring economic interdependencies. This overlooks the long-noted clustering into functional families—trend, momentum, volatility, volume, and chart-based tools.
2. **Accuracy–interpretability disconnect.** Prediction improves while description lags, keeping the accuracy–interpretability gap intact. Interpretability research is largely post hoc and seldom informs input design, especially in financial forecasting.
3. **Geographic sampling bias.** Most studies focus on the U.S. and China. Generalization to smaller but mature markets, such as NASDAQ Stockholm, remains largely untested.

Positioning. Corresponding to these three gaps, this thesis contributes:

- **Domain-informed taxonomy of technical indicators.** Develops a structured taxonomy over 24 single-asset technical indicators that systematizes fragmented functional groupings (trend, momentum, volatility, volume) in prior work and uses this taxonomy as an a priori constraint on feature selection.
- **PDR-grounded interpretability evaluation.** Evaluates models under Murdoch et al.’s PDR framework: out-of-sample R^2 for predictive accuracy (P); family-level selection patterns and stability checks for descriptive accuracy (D); and a qualitative assessment of practitioner usefulness at a 10-day horizon for relevancy (R).
- **Empirical benchmark for NASDAQ Stockholm.** Provides a BiLSTM-based forecasting study on NASDAQ Stockholm equities as an empirical benchmark for a mid-sized European stock exchange, complementing prior work that concentrates on U.S. and Chinese markets.

2.3 Summary

Existing research demonstrates that:

- Technical indicators can yield predictive signals, but evidence is inconsistent and often fragile once costs and robustness checks are applied, with more recent ML studies recovering only a small set of recurring, model-dependent signals.

- Conventional feature selection methods reduce dimensionality and can improve predictive performance, but treat indicators as flat variables and embed little financial theory.
- Existing classifications either operate at the market-wide level or provide only coarse, usage-driven groupings, rather than an explicit hierarchy over single-asset technical indicators.
- LSTM-based models have become widely used sequential baselines in recent forecasting studies, but interpretability is typically treated as a secondary, mostly post-hoc concern.

These observations motivate the domain-informed taxonomy of technical indicators, the BiLSTM-based modeling framework, and the PDR-grounded interpretability evaluation introduced in the next section.

3 Methodology

This section outlines the research design, data sources, feature engineering process, model architecture, and evaluation approach used in this study.

3.1 Research Approach

Design rationale and hypothesis. This study adopts Murdoch et al.’s definition of interpretability as “*the use of machine-learning models for the extraction of relevant knowledge about domain relationships contained in data*”. [32] In these terms, the present approach is a direct instantiation of Murdoch et al.’s notion of interpretability by sparsity through domain-informed modeling.

Building on this, the central hypothesis of the thesis is that a theory-driven taxonomy of technical indicators can enforce input-level sparsity by structuring feature selection around high-level families defined by economic function. By constraining the input space *ex ante*, the model’s decision space is reduced, so the source of signal is expected to become clearer, yielding a smaller, more auditable specification of the model while keeping out-of-sample predictive performance satisfactory.

The hypothesis is evaluated in a controlled experiment that contrasts indicator-wise and group-wise forward selection under the hold-out regimes described in Section 3.3.3. Outcomes are assessed under the PDR framework according to the protocol in Section 3.3.5, with the taxonomy serving as the main mechanism for embedding domain knowledge into the feature-selection process.

Construction of the indicator taxonomy. Section 2.1.4 showed that both academic studies and practitioner texts repeatedly organize technical tools into a small set of functional families, despite the absence of a directly reusable hierarchy over single-asset OHLCV-derived indicators. Building on that synthesis, this study operationalizes four of the families identified there—Trend, Momentum, Volatility, and Volume—as the top layer of a three-level indicator taxonomy. Chart-pattern and support/resistance tools, which form the fifth family in the broader technical-analysis tradition, are deliberately excluded from the present taxonomy because they encode geometric formations and price levels rather than scalar time-series transforms, and typically require dedicated pattern-recognition machinery; including them would substantially expand the design space and falls outside the scope of this work.

At the top level, the taxonomy comprises four economic families:

- **Trend** — indicators that characterise the prevailing direction and regime of prices over different horizons, typically via smoothing or breakout rules.
- **Momentum** — indicators that focus on the speed, persistence, and potential reversal of price movements relative to reference levels, often operationalized through oscillators or rate-of-change measures.
- **Volatility** — indicators that quantify the amplitude and clustering of price fluctuations, highlighting transitions between calm and turbulent regimes rather than the direction of movement.
- **Volume** — indicators that use trading activity to proxy for participation, liquidity, and the strength of buying or selling pressure, often by combining price changes with volume to infer accumulation or distribution.

Within each family, indicators are organized into two sub-groups that reflect more specific trading logic and naming conventions commonly used in empirical surveys and practitioner guides. The intermediate layer is therefore more fine-grained than the high-level families, yet coarser than individual indicators:

- **Trend:** *Filters* (moving-average type smoothers) and *Breakouts* (crossover and channel rules).
- **Momentum:** *Exhaustion signals* (overbought/oversold oscillators) and *Persistence* measures (multi-period rate-of-change and related transforms).
- **Volatility:** *Dispersion* measures (range, true range, and standard deviation) and *Envelopes* (band and channel constructions around price).
- **Volume:** *Cumulative flows* (accumulation/distribution-type series) and *Flow oscillators* (volume-weighted oscillators and turnover-based transforms).

This structure yields a three-level taxonomy (family → sub-group → indicator) that aligns with the economic roles summarised in Section 2.1.4 and provides a natural set of candidates for group-wise feature selection. Figure 3.1 gives a full overview of the resulting hierarchy.

Figure 3.1: Full three-level taxonomy of the 24 technical indicators used in this study, organized into four economic families (trend, momentum, volatility, volume), eight sub-groups, and individual indicators.

For readability purposes, the four main branches of the taxonomy are presented in Figures 3.2–3.5, each as a full-width diagram showing the family, its sub-groups, and associated indicators.

Figure 3.2: Trend family within the taxonomy, showing filter and breakout sub-groups and their associated indicators.

Figure 3.3: Momentum family within the taxonomy, showing exhaustion-signal and persistence sub-groups and their associated indicators.

Figure 3.4: Volatility family within the taxonomy, showing dispersion and envelope sub-groups and their associated indicators.

Figure 3.5: Volume family within the taxonomy, showing cumulative-flow and flow-oscillator sub-groups and their associated indicators.

Indicator set and definitions. The empirical analysis is based on a fixed universe of 24 technical indicators derived from the literature surveyed in Section 2.1.3. The selection balances three considerations: (i) empirical support, in the sense that each indicator has documented predictive relevance or persistent use in prior studies; (ii) coverage of the four families and eight sub-groups described above, so that major economic mechanisms

are represented without unnecessary redundancy; and (iii) practical implementability in a daily single-asset forecasting setup based on OHLCV data. Each indicator is assigned to exactly one sub-group and one family, ensuring that any feature-selection decision at the group level can be interpreted as a statement about which economic mechanisms the model relies on.

Table 3.4 lists the 24 indicators used in all experiments, together with their family and sub-group assignments, a brief justification for inclusion, and key supporting references from the technical-analysis and ML-finance literature.

Table 3.4: Technical indicators used in this study, grouped by family and sub-group.

Category	Sub-group	Feature	Justification
Trend	Filters	SMA (5)	Remain robust across 90 years of DJIA; profitability survives bootstrap and data-snooping tests [33, 41].
Trend	Filters	TEMA	Consistently ranked top trend filter across SVR, RF, LSTM, and XGBoost [43].
Trend	Filters	KAMA	Adaptive smoother resilient to noise; widely retained in indicator pools [42, 50].
Trend	Breakouts	50/200 SMA Crossover	Canonical breakout rule; replicated for decades across markets [33, 41].
Trend	Breakouts	MACD	Among the most studied crossover rules; central in ML-finance reviews [42, 49].
Trend	Breakouts	Ichimoku Cloud	Top-5 trend signal across tree- and neural-based evaluations [43].
Momentum	Exhaustion Signals	RSI (14)	Canonical oscillator; a consistent survivor in empirical and ML studies [49, 42].
Momentum	Exhaustion Signals	Stochastic Oscillator	Practitioner classic; replicated across decades of exhaustion-signal tests [41, 42].
Momentum	Exhaustion Signals	Price ROC (5)	Short-term ROC consistently retained in ML feature sets [42, 49].
Momentum	Persistence	HLC3	Dominant momentum input in feature-importance rankings [43].
Momentum	Persistence	RVI	Repeatedly top-ranked persistence signal across ML models [43].
Momentum	Persistence	Price ROC (20)	Long-horizon ROC capturing sustained momentum; replicated in reviews [41, 42].
Volatility	Dispersion	ATR (14)	Persistent “survivor” volatility measure across comparative studies [43].
Volatility	Dispersion	Rolling Std Dev	Foundational volatility measure; basis of ARCH/GARCH econometrics [34].

Table 3.4: Technical indicators used in this study (continued).

Category	Sub-group	Feature	Justification
Volatility	Dispersion	Price Distance	Frequently ranked top dispersion metric in ML comparisons [43].
Volatility	Envelopes	Bollinger Bands	Significant in- and out-of-sample predictive gains for equity risk premium [36].
Volatility	Envelopes	Keltner Channel	Distinct ATR-based envelope; retained in systematic reviews [42].
Volatility	Envelopes	Donchian Channel	Archetypal breakout envelope with long-documented profitability [41].
Volume	Cumulative Flows	OBV	Strong predictive slopes and positive out-of-sample R^2 [36].
Volume	Cumulative Flows	PVT	Top-3 volume feature across SVR, RF, XGBoost, and LSTM [43].
Volume	Cumulative Flows	CMF	Long-standing proxy for accumulation/distribution in surveys [42].
Volume	Flow Oscillators	MFI (14)	Consistently high feature importance; central in flow–momentum dynamics [43].
Volume	Flow Oscillators	Volume ROC (10)	Common turnover–momentum proxy in ML and systematic reviews [49].
Volume	Flow Oscillators	Chaikin Oscillator	Widely adopted flow oscillator capturing short-term accumulation/distribution shifts [42].

Task and experimental design. The predictive task is to forecast cumulative 10-day log returns for individual equities using a BiLSTM model under the two hold-out regimes described in Section 3.3.3. Two feature-selection strategies are compared:

- **Baseline:** forward selection on the full set of 24 technical indicators defined in Table 3.4.
- **Proposed approach:** taxonomy-based forward selection on groups of indicators, where candidate additions correspond to sub-groups in the taxonomy rather than individual indicators.

In both cases, the underlying network architecture, training procedure, and evaluation metrics are held fixed; only the feature-selection mechanism differs. The comparison is designed to isolate the effect of the taxonomy as a domain-informed constraint on the input space, and the resulting models are evaluated under the PDR framework in Section 3.3.5 to assess trade-offs between predictive performance, sparsity, and the alignment of selected features with economically meaningful indicator families.

3.2 Data Collection

3.2.1 Data Source & Scope

Daily stock data for all available tickers listed on NASDAQ Stockholm (as of 2024-01-01), including the constituents of the OMXS30 index (the 30 most-traded Swedish equities, widely used as a benchmark), were retrieved from Yahoo Finance using the `yfinance` package (v0.2.54) and processed with `pandas` (v2.2.3). Ticker symbols were standardized to Yahoo's naming convention (e.g., "ERIC S" → ERIC-B.ST) through a custom `format_ticker()` helper. For each symbol, the full available trading history was requested, covering data from the earliest listing date through 2025-01-01. For price data, the adjusted prices were used to account for dividends and stock splits.

3.2.2 Data Variables

Raw variables (fetched)

- Open — opening price recorded at the start of the trading day.
- High — highest traded price observed during the trading day.
- Low — lowest traded price observed during the trading day.
- Close — end-of-day price used as the reference point for return calculations.
- Volume — number of shares traded during the trading day.
- Dividends — cash dividend amount (per share) paid on that date, when applicable.
- Stock Splits — split factor applied on that date, capturing stock split events as reported by Yahoo Finance.

Derived variables (computed)

- Absolute Change — one-day change in the closing price, computed as $\text{Close}_t - \text{Close}_{t-1}$, capturing the raw price movement in currency units.
- Percentage Change — one-day percentage return, computed as $\frac{\text{Close}_t - \text{Close}_{t-1}}{\text{Close}_{t-1}} \times 100\%$, normalizing price changes across stocks with different price levels.

3.2.3 Data Retrieval Process

Data were retrieved through the `yfinance` API. To avoid rate-limit errors, a delay was introduced between consecutive calls. Raw files were stored in CSV format and later reloaded for preprocessing, including the addition of market-average return series.

3.2.4 Inclusion / Exclusion Criteria

Starting from the full set of OMX Stockholm tickers as of 2024-01-01, the following filters were applied to define the final sample:

- **Liquidity threshold:** $\leq 5\%$ of non-trading days.

- **Minimum viable trading history:** at least 1,000 data points (≈ 4 years) between 2015 and 2025 after dropping non-trading days.

Applying these filters reduced the initial set of 399 stocks to 287 (72%). A total of 55 stocks (14%) were excluded due to low liquidity and 57 (14%) due to insufficient trading history after removing non-trading days.

As an illustration, Appendix A provides a visualization of one representative stock after non-trading days were dropped and the filtering criteria were applied. The example highlights a consistent and continuous trading history, thereby demonstrating the intended effect of the applied thresholds.

3.3 Data Analysis

The training and validation data is segmented into overlapping 40-day windows with a 10-day stride, each used to predict cumulative 10-day log returns. The test data is segmented into overlapping 40-day windows with a 1-day stride to mirror deployment conditions where forecasts are produced daily. Normalization was applied using parameters estimated across the full training universe.

The target label is the cumulative 10-day log return, defined in Eq. (4):

$$y_t = \sum_{k=1}^{10} \log \left(\frac{P_{t+k}}{P_{t+k-1}} \right) = \log \left(\frac{P_{t+10}}{P_t} \right), \quad (4)$$

where P_t denotes the adjusted closing price at time t .

3.3.1 Feature Engineering

The feature set consists of 24 technical indicators that survived decades of econometric tests (see Section 2.1.1). Their inclusion and functional grouping are detailed in Table 3.4, which provides indicator-level justifications together with references to supporting literature. With the exception of the SMA-50-200 crossover (constructed manually), all indicators were generated with the `pandas-ta` library using default industry-aligned parameters.

3.3.2 Model Specification

This study relies on a BiLSTM as a stable state-of-the-art choice in financial forecasting between 2020–2025. Its configuration is as follows:

- **2 Layers:** Bidirectional LSTM layer + hidden head
- **Hidden units:** 64
- **Hidden head size:** 16
- **Hidden layer dropout:** 0.4
- **Hidden head dropout:** 0.6
- **Optimizer:** Adam with 10^{-4} learning rate and $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ weight decay.
- **Loss:** MSE

- **Training batch size:** 128
- **Validation batch size:** 256

Metrics. Training is optimized with MSE; model selection based on validation R_{batch}^2 (see Eq.5). Test performance is reported per-stock R_{stock}^2 (see Eq.6). For case studies, MAE/MSE deltas versus a trivial zero-return baseline are also reported (Section 4.1.4).

Training Procedure. Training runs for 20 epochs with an early stop after a total of 5 epochs with less than 10^{-4} improvement in the validation loss criterion. High dropout rates are applied to reduce overfitting under high noise-to-signal conditions common for log returns.

3.3.3 Analysis Techniques

Model evaluation relies on a combined temporal and cross-sectional split. 20 OMXS30 constituents and 80 non-OMXS30 stocks are randomly sampled from the full stock universe. Each is partitioned chronologically into a training set (90%) and a validation set (10%). To increase cross-sectional diversity, the validation set is supplemented with 5 additional OMXS30 and 20 additional non-OMXS30 stocks drawn from the same temporal horizon.

A held-out test set is then constructed from 5 OMXS30 and 20 non-OMXS30 stocks not included in training or validation. Two evaluation modes are applied:

- **Cross-sectional out-of-sample, temporal in-sample (CS-OOS/T-IS):** predictions are made over the full historical timeline of unseen stocks, including the initial 90% already covered by the training period.
- **Cross-sectional out-of-sample, temporal out-of-sample (CS-OOS/T-OOS):** predictions are restricted to the final 10% of the timeline for unseen stocks, i.e., both assets and horizons are new to the model.

Model performance is reported using the coefficient of determination (R^2). During training and validation, R^2 is computed with respect to the batch mean as in Eq. (5):

$$R_{\text{batch}}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \left(y_t^{(b)} - \hat{y}_t^{(b)} \right)^2}{\sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \left(y_t^{(b)} - \bar{y}^{(b)} \right)^2} \quad (5)$$

Where:

- $y_t^{(b)}$ = true value at time step t in batch b
- $\hat{y}_t^{(b)}$ = predicted value at time step t in batch b
- $\bar{y}^{(b)}$ = mean of true values in batch b
- B = number of batches
- T = number of time steps per batch

For evaluation on the held-out test set, R^2 is instead computed *per-stock* over its entire prediction horizon, using the stock-level mean $\bar{y}^{(s)}$ as in Eq. (6):

$$R_{\text{stock}}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \left(y_t^{(s)} - \hat{y}_t^{(s)} \right)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T \left(y_t^{(s)} - \bar{y}^{(s)} \right)^2} \quad (6)$$

Note that R^2 values can be negative when the model error exceeds the horizontal-mean baseline. While some studies clip negative R^2 at 0, this study reports them as-is since they convey information about generalization quality.

3.3.4 Feature Selection Logic

At each selection step, five models are trained with different random seeds, and the model with the highest validation R_{batch}^2 is selected (*best-of-5*). No halting criterion is applied, as early peaks can reflect unstable local optima under noise. When a group is selected during group-wise forward selection, all indicators in that group are included at once. Thus, the group-wise selection adds 6 indicators per step. Test-set results are presented in tables and figures solely for ex-post interpretation and are not used for model selection.

3.3.5 Evaluation Under the PDR Framework

Following Murdoch et al., this study evaluates interpretability through the Predictive (P), Descriptive (D), Relevant (R) framework.

- **Predictive (P).** Compare out-of-sample R^2 and MSE under the two hold-out regimes defined in Section 3.3.3.
- **Descriptive (D).** Qualitatively assess model parsimony and transparency stemming from the selection process: (a) number of selected groups vs. individual indicators; (b) stability of selected groups across the hold-out regimes; (c) alignment of selected groups with their stated economic functions. These provide a structured account of *what* the model uses and *why* the final specification is simpler.
- **Relevant (R).** Qualitatively assess domain meaningfulness by checking whether the direction of effects accords with financial theory.

Under PDR, success means improving D and/or R while keeping P satisfactory; modest declines in P are acceptable when accompanied by clear gains in D or R.

3.4 Reliability and Validity

To ensure model generalizability and methodological rigor, the following controls were implemented:

- **Overfitting prevention:** dropout rates of 0.4 and 0.6, unusually high by common practice, were selected to mitigate the overfitting observed with lower values under high noise-to-signal conditions.
- **Reproducibility:** fixed seeds, saved models, and pinned dependency versions. Code and config files are available upon request.
- **Bias control:** prevention of future leakage through lagged features, with all indicators constructed solely from past data.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The study relies exclusively on public historical data and does not involve personal financial interests or sensitive data. Results are not intended as investment advice but as an academic exercise in methodological evaluation.

3.6 Summary

This section outlined the experimental pipeline for evaluating whether domain-informed feature selection can improve both the accuracy and interpretability of deep-learning stock return forecasts. Flat forward selection is contrasted with taxonomy-constrained selection to test if theory-grounded indicator hierarchies enhance predictive performance while making feature contributions more transparent. Data collection, filtering, and splitting ensured a representative and unbiased sample, and all model, feature, and selection logic was fully scripted for reproducibility. Together, these measures provide a rigorous framework for assessing the role of financial domain knowledge in deep-learning time-series forecasting and form the basis for the results presented in Section 4.

4 Results and Analysis

This section presents the findings of the study, followed by an analysis and interpretation of the results. The Results section provides raw data in an objective manner without interpretation, while the Analysis section gives meaning to the data, explores patterns, and derives conclusions backed by statistical or qualitative reasoning.

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Preliminary Findings from Setup Exploration

Before running the main experiment, a series of exploratory trials were conducted to identify a configuration that produced stable training dynamics. These trials were not intended for hypothesis testing but to establish workable defaults for the BiLSTM pipeline. Different dropout levels (0.2–0.8) revealed that lower values caused overfitting while higher values collapsed learning, leading to the choice of 0.4 for the BiLSTM layer and 0.6 for the hidden head. Batch sizes (32–256) were tested, with 128 for training and 256 for validation offering the best trade-off between noise sensitivity and oversmoothing. Learning rates (10^{-3} – 10^{-5}) and hidden sizes (16–128) were also tested; a rate of 10^{-4} with hidden size 64 gave the most stable convergence, while a hidden head of 16 was the only configuration that avoided instability. Finally, adding additional BiLSTM layers consistently reduced stability without performance gains, so the final architecture was kept shallow.

Normalization. Three normalization strategies were assessed under a 90/10 train/validation split with the full set of 24 indicators:

1. **Per-window** — mean and standard deviation are computed within each sliding window and used only for that window.
2. **Per-stock** — mean and standard deviation are computed on each stock’s training history and reused for that stock across train, validation, and test.
3. **Per-universe** — a single mean and standard deviation are computed on the entire training universe and applied to all stocks.

Figures 4.6–4.8 show that none of the normalization modes produced positive validation R_{batch}^2 . Per-universe performed best ($-0.0540 R_{\text{batch}}^2$), followed by per-window ($-0.0585 R_{\text{batch}}^2$) and per-stock ($-0.0942 R_{\text{batch}}^2$).

Figure 4.6: Per-window normalization under 90/10 split R_{batch}^2 score for 24 indicators

Figure 4.7: Per-stock normalization under 90/10 split R_{batch}^2 score for 24 indicators

Figure 4.8: Per-universe normalization under 90/10 split R^2_{batch} score for 24 indicators

Out-of-sample evaluation. Figure 4.9 demonstrates similar patterns for CS-OOS/T-OOS 90/10 split hold-out across the normalization modes. Per-window and per-stock scaling delivered near-zero performance. Universe-level normalization yielded slightly stronger but unstable results, with a median R^2_{stock} of 2.1%, a mean of -10.5% , and a standard deviation of 46% —substantially above the variability observed for per-window (34.8%) and per-stock (34.3%) normalization.

Figure 4.9: CS-OOS/T-OOS 90/10 split Test R^2_{stock} performance per normalization mode

4.1.2 Forward Selection Experiments

Training Instability. Forward selection was applied at both the individual-indicator level and the high-level groups. In both cases, *best-of-5* validation R_{batch}^2 displayed high volatility, with values fluctuating noticeably between steps.

Figures 4.10–4.11 show spikes in the mean test R_{stock}^2 curves in the indicator-wise selection: an early jump in explanatory power when 2-3 features were included, followed by a decline and partial recovery, and a second, larger increase when the full set of 24 indicators was used. These patterns were not consistently reflected in validation R_{batch}^2 , which remained largely flat. Visual inspection shows seemingly no correlation between validation R_{batch}^2 and mean test R_{stock}^2 . Performance gaps are as high as 0.1571 for mean R_{stock}^2 and 0.0678 for median R_{stock}^2 .

Figure 4.10: Validation R_{batch}^2 and test mean R_{stock}^2 across indicator-wise selection steps

Figure 4.11: Validation R_{batch}^2 and test median R_{stock}^2 across indicator-wise selection steps

Figures 4.12–4.13 show similar patterns for group-wise selection, with the largest differences between R_{batch}^2 and R_{stock}^2 being 0.1391 for mean R_{stock}^2 and 0.0271 for median R_{stock}^2 .

Figure 4.12: Validation R_{batch}^2 and test mean R_{stock}^2 across group-wise selection steps

Figure 4.13: Validation R_{batch}^2 and test median R_{stock}^2 across group-wise selection steps

Forward Selection on Indicators. Table 4.5 shows minimal correlation between validation and test performance in *best-of-5 runs*. The top three results for each indicator type are highlighted in cyan, with shading intensity denoting rank (darkest = best, lightest = 3rd best).

On the test set, the highest-performing feature set included all 24 indicators; the second-best used 2 (1 Volatility, 1 Trend); and the third-best used 7 (2 Volatility, 1 Trend, 3 Volume, 1 Momentum). By contrast, the top validation set result selected 17 indicators (3 Volatility, 5 Trend, 4 Volume, 5 Momentum); the second-best selected 7 (2 Volatility,

1 Trend, 3 Volume, 1 Momentum); and the third-best selected 3 (1 Volatility, 1 Trend, 1 Volume).

In exploratory reruns with different random seeds, the greedy forward-selection paths themselves also differed, both in the order in which indicators were included and in which intermediate configurations appeared locally optimal under validation R_{batch}^2 .

Table 4.5: Stepwise Indicator Inclusion with Validation R_{batch}^2 and Test R_{stock}^2 on 90/10 split.

Step	Indicator Added	Val R_{batch}^2	Test R_{stock}^2 (Mean)	Test R_{stock}^2 (Median)
1	Bollinger Bands	-0.0031	-0.1160	-0.0137
2	KAMA	0.0006	-0.0787	0.0182
3	Volume ROC (10)	0.0012	-0.0923	-0.0020
4	MFI (14)	0.0003	-0.1240	-0.0116
5	Chaikin Oscillator	-0.0001	-0.1111	-0.0220
6	Price ROC (20)	-0.0003	-0.1259	-0.0196
7	Price Distance	0.0038	-0.0904	-0.0002
8	HLC3	-0.0015	-0.1109	-0.0188
9	SMA (5)	-0.0021	-0.1168	0.0004
10	RSI (14)	-0.0012	-0.1154	-0.0024
11	ATR (14)	-0.0009	-0.0978	0.0024
12	RVI (14)	-0.0014	-0.1442	-0.0442
13	TEMA (10)	-0.0021	-0.1072	-0.0197
14	SMA Crossover 50/200	-0.0022	-0.1267	-0.0104
15	PVT	-0.0025	-0.1506	-0.0514
16	Stochastic Oscillator	-0.0022	-0.1245	-0.0159
17	MACD	0.0014	-0.1557	-0.0664
18	Donchian Channel	-0.0034	-0.1111	-0.0016
19	Keltner Channel	-0.0028	-0.1235	-0.0092
20	OBV	-0.0035	-0.1265	-0.0198
21	Rolling Std Dev (30)	0.0000	-0.1334	-0.0209
22	CMF (20)	-0.0035	-0.1050	0.0091
23	Price ROC (5)	-0.0049	-0.1326	-0.0099
24	Ichimoku Cloud	-0.0059	-0.0767	0.0233

Best indicator combination. Table 4.6 summarizes the individual indicators present in the model at the validation step with the highest R_{batch}^2 during indicator-wise forward selection. For each high-level family in the taxonomy, only those indicators that were actually selected by the procedure at that step are listed.

Table 4.6: Indicators picked at the best per-val R_{batch}^2 step during forward selection on technical indicators.

Group	Indicators Added
Trend	KAMA, SMA5, TEMA (10), SMA Crossover 50/200, MACD
Momentum	Price ROC (20), HLC3, RSI(14), RVI (14), Stochastic Oscillator
Volatility	Bollinger Bands, Price Distance, ATR (14)
Volume	Volume ROC (10), MFI(14), Chaikin Oscillator, PVT

Forward Selection on Taxonomy. Table 4.7 summarizes stepwise inclusion of high-level families under taxonomy-constrained forward selection. As in the indicator-wise setting, validation and test performance do not move in lockstep: only at step 2 does the highest validation R_{batch}^2 coincide with the best mean and median test R_{stock}^2 . The best-performing feature set emphasizes Volume and Volatility as the dominant groups, and the corresponding result is highlighted in cyan.

Table 4.7: Stepwise High Level Group Inclusion with Validation R_{batch}^2 and Test R_{stock}^2 on 90/10 split.

Step	Group Added	Val R_{batch}^2	Test R_{stock}^2 (Mean)	Test R_{stock}^2 (Median)
1	Volume	-0.0061	-0.1376	-0.0087
2	Volatility	-0.0027	-0.0815	0.0244
3	Momentum	-0.0033	-0.1424	-0.0171
4	Trend	-0.0056	-0.1136	0.0056

Best group combination. Table 4.8 summarizes the indicators present in the model at the validation step with the highest R_{batch}^2 during group-wise forward selection. Once a high-level family is selected in this procedure, all of its member indicators as defined by the taxonomy enter the model and are listed for that family.

Table 4.8: Indicators picked at the best per-val R_{batch}^2 step during forward selection on groups of technical indicators.

Group	Indicators Added
Volatility	ATR (14), Rolling Std Dev (30), Price Distance, Bollinger Bands, Keltner Channel, Donchian Channel
Volume	CMF (20), OBV, PVT, MFI (14), Volume ROC (10), Chaikin Oscillator

Differences between selections. Table 4.9 compares the best per-validation steps under indicator-wise and taxonomy-constrained selection. Test performance differed meaningfully between the two modes, with taxonomy-constrained selection producing higher test R_{stock}^2 than indicator-level selection. At the indicator level, the feature sets chosen at the best validation step were generally balanced, drawing comparable numbers from each group (see Table 4.5). However, when viewed ex post by test performance, the preferred combinations leaned toward Volume and Volatility—closely matching the group-level selection in Table 4.7, which identified these two as the strongest pair on the training, validation, and test sets.

Table 4.9: Comparison of results for the best step across both selection modes.

Step	Selection Mode	Val R_{batch}^2	Test R_{stock}^2 (Mean)	Test R_{stock}^2 (Median)
17	Indicator (best per-val)	0.14%	-15.6%	-6.6%
2	Group (best per-val)	-0.59%	-8.1%	2.4%

4.1.3 Stability Tests

High Model Instability. Table 4.10 reports *mean-of-5 model* reruns using the indicators from the best steps under each selection mode. The results suggest a positive association between validation R_{batch}^2 and test R_{stock}^2 , but also substantial variability in both metrics: standard deviations across runs range from 8.8% to 10.9%. Additionally, the *mean-of-5* test with all 24 indicators failed to produce a single run with positive performance, contradicting earlier findings in Section 4.1.2. The top three results for each indicator type are highlighted in cyan, with shading intensity denoting rank (darkest = best, lightest = 3rd best).

Table 4.10: Comparison of Results for Best Step Across Both Selection Modes.

Step	Selection Mode	Val R_{batch}^2 (Mean-of-5)	Test R_{stock}^2 (Mean-of-5)	Test R_{stock}^2 (Median-of-5)	Test R_{stock}^2 Std	> 0 R_{stock}^2 (Mean No)	> 0 R_{stock}^2 (Median No)
24	Indicator (best per-test)	-0.0897	-0.2706	-0.0907	0.1086	0	0
17	Indicator (best per-val)	-0.0423	-0.1699	-0.0496	0.0862	0	2
2	Group (best per-val)	-0.0341	-0.1491	-0.0392	0.0885	0	2

Score Curves. Figures 4.14–4.16 show *mean-of-5* score curves for the three feature combinations. In all cases, they follow the textbook pattern: R_{batch}^2 rises rapidly at the start and then plateaus shortly after. Across all three combinations, validation R_{batch}^2 plateaued just below zero and did not cross that threshold on average.

Figure 4.14: Per-test best indicator selection step (Mean-of-5 R_{batch}^2 score)

Figure 4.15: Per-val best indicator selection step (Mean-of-5 R_{batch}^2 score)

Figure 4.16: Per-val best group selection step (Mean-of-5 R_{batch}^2 score)

4.1.4 Test-Set Evaluation

CS-OOS/T-OOS Generalization. Figure 4.17 summarizes CS-OOS/T-OOS 90/10 split performance for the best steps under each selection mode. Overall performance was modest but non-random. Within the forward selection runs, the Volatility+Volume group achieved a median R^2_{stock} of 2.4% and a mean of -8.2% across 25 unseen stocks on unseen temporal horizons; 14 of the 25 stocks showed positive R^2_{stock} . In contrast, the best indicator-level step with 17 inputs achieved a median of -6.6% , a mean of -15.6% , and only 2 of 25 stocks above zero R^2_{stock} .

Figure 4.17: CS-OOS/T-OOS 90/10 split hold-out test R^2_{stock} for the best selection steps across 2 selection modes

CS-OOS/T-OOS Best Stock. Figure 4.18 shows the strongest individual CS-OOS/T-OOS result for the Volatility+Volume group, explaining 9.35% of the variance in stock log returns. The predicted trajectory closely resembles the structure of the actual series. Relative to the trivial baseline of zero log returns, the model's errors were smaller, with the baseline being 11.1% higher in MSE and 9.3% higher in MAE.

Figure 4.18: Test R_{stock}^2 for Volatility + Volume Group for SAGA-D

CS-OOS/T-OOS Worst Stock. Figure 4.19 illustrates the weakest CS-OOS/T-OOS result for the same Volatility+Volume group, with $R^2_{\text{stock}} = -144.25\%$ indicating severe misalignment with the target. Yet, even in this case, the model outperformed the trivial baseline of zero log returns, with baseline errors higher by 15.4% in MSE and 8.3% in MAE—suggesting that it still captured some non-random structure and reduced raw prediction error.

Figure 4.19: Test R^2_{stock} for Volatility + Volume Group for KFAST-B

CS-OOS/T-IS Generalization. Figure 4.20 summarizes CS-OOS/T-IS 90/10 split performance for the best steps under each selection mode. When predicting unseen stocks on the seen temporal horizon, generalization was stronger: 22 of 25 test stocks achieved positive R^2_{stock} , indicating more reliable transfer across assets than across time. For the Volatility+Volume group, the best-performing combination, the median variance explained was 2.5% and the mean was 2.2%. By contrast, the best indicator-level selection step produced weaker results, with a mean of -1.6% , a median of -1.7% , and only 8 of 25 stocks showing positive R^2_{stock} .

Figure 4.20: CS-OOS/T-IS 90/10 split hold-out test R^2_{stock} for the best selection steps across 2 selection modes

CS-OOS/T-IS Best Stock. Figure 4.21 shows the strongest CS-OOS/T-IS result for the Volatility+Volume group, achieving 9.22% variance explained—coincidentally on the same stock (SAGA-D) as in the CS-OOS/T-OOS hold-out. Relative to the trivial baseline of zero log returns, the model’s errors were smaller, with the baseline being 9.7% higher in MSE and 6.3% higher in MAE.

Figure 4.21: Test R^2_{stock} for Volatility + Volume Group for SAGA-D

CS-OOS/T-IS Worst Stock. Figure 4.22 presents the weakest CS-OOS/T-IS result for the Volatility+Volume group, with $R^2_{\text{stock}} = -16.7\%$ and visible misrepresentation of both the mean level and the overall series shape. Relative to the baseline, errors were larger, with baseline MSE lower by 15.1% and MAE lower by 9.7%.

Figure 4.22: Test R^2_{stock} for Volatility + Volume Group for ATCO-A

4.2 Analysis

This subsection interprets the numerical results reported in Section 4.1. It first examines where predictive signal appears to concentrate across the indicator families and how different normalization and hold-out schemes affect generalization. It then evaluates these findings under the Predictive–Descriptive–Relevant (PDR) framework.

4.2.1 General Analysis

Overall Stability of Results. The results reveal a weak but non-random predictive structure in the Swedish equity market. Across repeated runs, models occasionally achieved positive test R_{stock}^2 , but the outcomes were unstable. Table 4.10 reports that the standard deviation of test R_{stock}^2 across five independent runs ranged from 0.086 to 0.109, depending on the feature set. This means that a model trained on one split may appear successful, while the same configuration trained on a different initialization or slightly shifted split may fail. The instability is also evident in the learning curves. Figures 4.14–4.16 display smooth *mean-of-5* training and validation score curves, which converge steadily with R_{batch}^2 rising in parallel. By contrast, Figures 4.10–4.13 plot *best-of-5* forward-selection steps, where test R_{stock}^2 fluctuates independently of validation R_{batch}^2 performance. Taken together, these results indicate that predictive signals exist but are fragile, making single-run outcomes unreliable as evidence of generalization.

Feature Group Contributions. A clearer pattern emerged in the relative strength of feature groups. Group-wise forward selection isolated Volume and Volatility as the most informative features: performance peaked once these two groups were included, and declined when momentum and trend were added in later steps (Table 4.7). This suggests that directional indicators not only contributed little additional signal but, in fact, introduced noise that reduced generalization. On the strictest split, where both assets and horizons were unseen, the Volume+Volatility combination reached a median test R_{stock}^2 of 2.4%, compared to near-zero and negative values once momentum and trend were added.

Indicator-wise vs Group-wise Selection. The per-indicator selection results in Table 4.5 did not show this pattern as clearly when evaluated by validation performance. The step with the highest validation R_{batch}^2 drew features from all four groups almost evenly (Table 4.6), masking the concentration of signal in Volume and Volatility. Only when test performance was considered—an approach that involves data snooping—did the preference for Volume and Volatility become visible. The fact that group-wise selection revealed this structure without relying on test outcomes, while indicator-wise selection required retrospective peeking, reinforces the view that grouping indicators by domain helps uncover signal that would otherwise be obscured.

Sequence Dependence and Group-Level Stability. At the same time, the indicator-wise forward-selection procedure is not stable at the level of individual features. In exploratory reruns with different random seeds, the stepwise inclusion paths changed, with different indicators entering at different steps and different intermediate subsets appearing locally optimal under validation R_{batch}^2 . Given the weak signal and the stochastic nature of BiLSTM training, this variability is expected, and the specific indicator order in Table 4.5 should not be interpreted as a unique ranking of individual predictors. When these paths are viewed at the level of the four high-level families, however, a more stable pattern

emerges: the best-performing indicator-wise configurations by test R_{stock}^2 concentrate on indicators from the Volume and Volatility groups, matching the best group-wise combination. This consistency suggests that, under the present experimental conditions, changing the forward-selection sequence mainly affects the exact indicator membership and ordering, while leaving the dominant group composition—Volume+Volatility—largely unchanged.

Validation–Test Alignment Another consistent finding was the unstable relationship between validation and test performance. When models were ranked by their single best run (*best-of-5*), validation R_{batch}^2 did not correlate with test R_{stock}^2 , with forward-selection steps showing gains in validation that often coincided with flat or negative test outcomes (Figures 4.10–4.13, Table 4.5). In contrast, when results were averaged across five independent runs (*mean-of-5*), a positive correlation emerged, with higher validation scores tending to correspond to higher test scores on average (Table 4.10). This indicates that transferable signal exists, but it is fragile: run-to-run variance is high enough to obscure it in single instances, making individual validation improvements unreliable as evidence of true generalization.

Full Set vs Subsets of Indicators. An additional observation is that models including all 24 indicators sometimes outperformed those built on narrower subsets. Table 4.5 shows that in the *best-of-5* runs the full feature set achieved higher test R_{stock}^2 than any reduced indicator combination for indicator-wise selection. Similarly, Table 4.7 indicates that the full set was the only configuration besides the best Volume+Volatility combination to produce a positive test R_{stock}^2 for group-wise selection. However, this effect was not consistent. As reported in Table 4.10, both mean and median performance across five independent runs (*mean-of-5*) were stronger for smaller feature subsets—both in group-wise and indicator-wise selection—than for the full 24-indicator set. Moreover, as evident in Table 4.10, the 24-indicator set failed to produce a single run positive in mean or median R_{stock}^2 performance across five different runs, suggesting that the high performance of 24-indicator set displayed in Tables 4.5 and 4.7 is the result of a lucky draw.

Cross-Sectional vs Temporal Generalization. Cross-sectional generalization appeared numerically stronger, but, looking at the plots of worst-case stock predictions, temporal splits preserved more structure. Figures 4.17 and 4.20 show that while median performance across splits was similar, the cross-sectional evaluation produced a tighter distribution, partly because its longer horizon (10 years) disperses errors across more data. Yet under the strictest condition, results diverged: cross-sectional hold-outs sometimes collapsed to near-constant noise, explaining -16.7% of the variance (Figure 4.22), whereas temporal hold-outs, though far worse numerically (-140.27% R_{stock}^2 over 1 year, Figure 4.19), still reflected recognizable series dynamics. This contrast indicates that cross-sectional evaluation benefits statistically from longer horizons but can mask structurally empty predictions, while temporal splits amplify noise over shorter spans but retain some underlying dynamics even in the worst cases.

Normalization Effects. Normalization experiments reinforced this interpretation. Figures 4.6–4.8 illustrate that per-universe scaler fitting for z-score normalization consistently produced the strongest out-of-sample results, being the only out of 3 types that achieved positive median test R_{stock}^2 for the full set of 24 indicators during preliminary

experiments. By contrast, per-stock and per-window normalization eliminated cross-sectional variation and achieved strictly negative test R_{stock}^2 . These differences demonstrate that relative positioning of assets within the market carries more predictive information than isolated or window-specific transformations, and that preserving this context is essential for uncovering whatever weak signal exists.

Summary. Taken together, these findings indicate that technical indicators provide limited but non-random predictive power. The signal is strongest when features preserve cross-sectional structure, when models are averaged across multiple runs, and when performance is evaluated over longer horizons. However, the predictive patterns remain fragile, with high variance across runs and weak transferability across time.

4.2.2 Evaluation under PDR

This section evaluates P, D, and R based on analysis from Section 4.2.1 and results from Section 4.1 per the evaluation protocol defined in Section 3.3.5.

Predictive Accuracy (P). Predictive performance remains satisfactory relative to the baseline across both hold-out regimes. Group-wise forward selection is on par to *slightly* higher than the indicator-wise baseline as summarized by Tables 4.9 and 4.10; however, the difference lies within the observed run-to-run variability (standard deviation of test R_{stock}^2 across five runs ≈ 0.086 – 0.109 in Table 4.10, with instability also visible in Figures 4.10–4.13). Accordingly, P is classified as preserved rather than improved for the stated trade-off.

Descriptive Accuracy (D). The taxonomy-constrained specification uses fewer input families, fewer total indicators and makes the model’s reliance on particular families explicit. Across both hold-out regimes, the same few families recur—most notably Volume and Volatility—while Trend and Momentum appear sporadically (Section 4.2.1, “Feature Group Contributions”; also Tables 4.6 and 4.8). This yields a smaller, clearer family-level narrative *on average*, though selection stability is only partial given the reported variance across seeds/splits (Table 4.10). Therefore, D is classified as *improved on average*.

Relevance (R). For 10-day returns, families capturing trading activity and risk (Volume/Volatility) are expected to be more informative than longer-horizon Trend/Momentum effects. The taxonomy-driven selections and their directions align with these short-horizon expectations, as evidenced by (i) performance peaking once *Volume+Volatility* are included and declining when *Trend/Momentum* are added (Table 4.7; Section 4.2.1, “Feature Group Contributions” and “Indicator-wise vs Group-wise Selection”), and (ii) normalization results showing that preserving cross-sectional structure strengthens out-of-sample performance (Figures 4.6–4.8; Section 4.2.1, “Normalization Effects”). On R, the interpretations are judged as *relevant* to the forecasting task and audience.

Verdict. As defined in Section 3.3.5, success means improving D and/or R while keeping P satisfactory. Here, D improves and R is satisfied, while P remains satisfactory (preserved). However, these interpretability gains should be read with caution: the signal is fragile and run-to-run variability is non-trivial (Table 4.10; Figures 4.10–4.13). Therefore, the PDR trade-off is met *on average*, not guaranteed per run or split.

5 Discussion

This section interprets the empirical results in light of the research objectives and the existing literature. It first revisits the six objectives defined in Section 1.4 and summarizes how the experiments addressed them, then draws broader insights about generalization, model stability, and the trade-off between predictive and descriptive accuracy. Finally, it situates the findings within interpretability frameworks and prior work and outlines the main limitations of the study.

5.1 Revisiting Research Objectives

Table 1.2 in Section 1.4 defined six research objectives. Their outcomes can be summarized as follows:

- **O1 Taxonomy.** A domain-informed taxonomy was constructed and justified on the basis of prior financial-economics and technical-analysis literature, grouping 24 indicators into four families (Trend, Momentum, Volatility, Volume) and operationalized as an ex-ante design constraint for group-wise feature selection.
- **O2 Forward selection.** Implemented at both indicator and group levels; group-wise runs consistently favored Volume and Volatility, while Trend and Momentum diluted performance.
- **O3 Forecasting performance.** Across both cross-sectional and temporal hold-out regimes, out-of-sample stock-wise R^2 and MSE were quantified for BiLSTM models under indicator-wise and taxonomy-constrained forward selection; on the strict temporal test set, the taxonomy-constrained variant achieved higher median R_{stock}^2 ($\approx 2.4\%$ vs. -6.6%), although gains were modest and unstable.
- **O4 Interpretability.** The taxonomy yielded a smaller, clearer family-level specification and a consistent *on-average* contribution pattern (Volume/Volatility recurrent; Trend/Momentum sporadic), improving descriptive accuracy while keeping predictive accuracy broadly comparable and supporting a plausible practitioner narrative at the 10-day horizon.
- **O5 Normalization.** Per-universe scaling preserved cross-sectional structure and yielded weak but transferable signals; per-stock and per-window normalization consistently underperformed.
- **O6 Generalization.** Cross-sectional evaluation produced numerically stronger results but sometimes degenerated into trivial predictions, while temporal evaluation was harsher yet preserved structural dynamics.

In sum, under the stated PDR framework, descriptive accuracy improves, predictive accuracy remains broadly comparable to the baseline (and in some cases modestly improves), and relevancy is satisfied. Because variance across runs is non-trivial, these conclusions are *average-case* rather than per-run guarantees. Interpreted this way, the taxonomy functions as an ex-ante, domain-based constraint that improves interpretability.

5.2 Insights from Experimental Results

Indicator families. The dominance of *Volume* and *Volatility* families indicates that short-horizon forecasts are primarily informed by market participation and dispersion rather than by trend persistence. This suggests that liquidity conditions and short-term risk perceptions embed weak but transferable signals even in relatively efficient markets. By contrast, trend-following and momentum rules, which rely on the persistence of medium-term price dynamics, contributed noise at the 10-day horizon. The resulting dilution of predictive power is consistent with evidence that momentum effects operate at longer horizons. Jegadeesh and Titman [10] documented significant abnormal returns over 3-12 month holding periods, and Carhart [6] confirmed momentum as a 1-year factor, though largely absorbed by transaction costs and factor exposures. The absence of such effects at the daily-to-weekly horizon explains why Trend and Momentum failed to add value in this setting. These findings refine prior reviews that emphasize fragility [41, 42, 50] by showing that predictive content is not only rare but systematically tied to family type and horizon. The value here is not larger accuracy per se, but a clearer account of *when* and *which* families matter at short horizons.

Normalization. These outcomes highlight that normalization choices are not mere pre-processing details but shape the very availability of predictive content. Per-universe scaling preserved the relative positioning of stocks within the market, thereby retaining cross-sectional information about flows and dispersion, and produced modest but positive results. In contrast, per-stock and per-window scaling eliminated these relationships by re-centering each series in isolation, leading to consistently negative outcomes. The implication is that predictive information in technical indicators is fundamentally relational, depending on a stock’s position relative to others. This resonates with equity risk premium research, where predictive power often arises from differences across assets rather than from individual series alone. [36]

Generalization. Hold-out design produced contrasting outcomes. Cross-sectional splits generated more favorable numerical performance, but in several cases forecasts degenerated into noise that lacked structural meaning despite positive R_{stock}^2 . Temporal splits, though numerically harsher, preserved meaningful dynamics and provided a more credible test of robustness. Cross-sectional splits can overstate success by hiding degeneracy, whereas temporal splits expose fragility but make wins more believable. When conclusions diverge, we treat the temporal evidence as the stricter test.

Model stability. Instability across seeds was substantial, with performance ranging from modestly positive to strongly negative. Only after aggregating across runs did consistent insights emerge. Forward selection amplified instability by optimizing on validation peaks, which did not transfer reliably to test performance. This weak correlation between validation and test outcomes demonstrates that apparent breakthroughs can reflect statistical variance rather than genuine signal, underscoring the need for stability checks and aggregation in financial ML. These observations echo concerns in the literature about data-snooping and fragile inference in technical analysis [33, 41], and demonstrate that robust conclusions require stability checks and aggregation rather than reliance on best-case outcomes.

Interpretability Gains. The taxonomy clarifies where signal resides: performance typically peaks when Volume and Volatility enter, and drifts when Trend/Momentum are added. Occasional *best-of-5* outperformance by the full 24-indicator set does not survive aggregation and is therefore treated as instability rather than evidence of a richer specification. One plausible explanation is *within-family redundancy*: selecting fewer families but allowing multiple, partly collinear indicators inside each family gives the model several views of the same underlying process (trading activity and risk), which—under weak signal—acts like variance reduction or regularization. Under this interpretation, concentrating capacity on a small number of economically coherent families and limiting cross-family degrees of freedom helps the model capture the common component more reliably while avoiding noise introduced by standalone features from other families. This mechanism is best viewed as a hypothesis consistent with the observed patterns rather than as a formally tested causal claim. The practical value is a simpler, more legible input story and behavior that is more stable on average.

5.3 Interpretability in Context

Interpretability in machine learning is a contested concept that carries multiple and sometimes conflicting definitions [26]. In this thesis, interpretability is defined as a structural design choice: the feature space was organized *ex ante* into economically meaningful families so that inputs are auditable and the model’s sources of signal are explicit. This approach satisfies the definition of interpretability through domain-informed feature space sparsity proposed by Murdoch et al. [32]

The results are assessed under the PDR framework proposed by Murdoch et al. (2019). [32] Predictive accuracy stayed satisfactory, with taxonomy-constrained selection improving descriptive accuracy while retaining relevancy.

The taxonomy highlights systematic contributions of families that would otherwise be obscured by indicator-wise selection. This function is analogous to the role of intelligible model structures discussed by Caruana et al. [63], who emphasize that transparency and performance need not be mutually exclusive. In the present case, taxonomy acts as a factor-like decomposition of technical indicators, clarifying where predictive content resides and where it fails to emerge. This demonstrates that interpretability can be operationalized through domain-informed structuring of features, rather than relying exclusively on post-hoc methods.

5.4 Comparison with Prior Work

Most forecasting studies in this domain have emphasized accuracy metrics as the primary benchmark of success. Reviews such as Bustos and Pomares-Quimbaya [50] and Nti et al. [49] largely focus on whether models achieve higher returns or lower error, with limited attention to interpretability. This thesis adds a structured, domain-informed feature design so that indicator behavior can be compared at the family level rather than indicator-by-indicator. The taxonomy-driven approach aligns with interpretability frameworks in machine learning, which stress that the value of a model lies not only in predictive performance but also in its ability to provide structured, intelligible insights.

The findings on indicator families are consistent with prior assessments of technical indicators in machine learning. Fang et al. [42] concluded that most indicators do not withstand robustness checks, with only a narrow subset offering stable predictive value. Mostafavi and Hooman [43] reached similar conclusions using clustering approaches, where volatility- and volume-based groups emerged as consistently informative. The

present results reinforce these observations: predictive content concentrated in the same families, while trend and momentum signals offered limited value at short horizons.

The observed weak but non-random predictive signal also parallels evidence from both machine learning and classical rule-based studies. Murray et al. [25] demonstrated that charting by machines uncovers faint but persistent structures in price series, even if effect sizes remain modest. Earlier rule-based analyses, such as Brock et al. [33], documented statistically significant gains from simple moving-average and trading-range rules, while Park and Irwin [41] found that profitability evidence, though widespread, was fragile and highly sensitive to methodology. The instability and variance encountered in the present experiments are consistent with this pattern, supporting the conclusion that technical signals exist but are precarious.

Connections also emerge with the equity risk premium literature. Neely et al. [36] showed that technical indicators rival and sometimes exceed macroeconomic variables in forecasting excess returns, highlighting their potential to contribute weak but transferable signals. Finally, Carhart [6] established momentum as a systematic factor in asset pricing, reinforcing that some technical constructs reflect broader market dynamics rather than isolated anomalies. In a similar way, the taxonomy adopted here reveals family-level structures that function similarly to factor decompositions, clarifying that predictive content is not evenly distributed but concentrated in systematic groups such as Volume and Volatility. This situates taxonomy-driven selection as a bridge between classical factor decompositions and modern ML approaches, offering a structured way to interpret technical indicators.

In addition, most of the empirical evidence is drawn from U.S. or Chinese markets, whereas the present study documents analogous weak-but-structured technical signals in NASDAQ Stockholm, a mid-sized European exchange. This suggests that the combination of fragile overall predictability and concentrated family-level contributions is not unique to the largest markets, even though the strength of the effects remains modest.

5.5 Limitations

This study faces several limitations:

- **Market scope.** The analysis was restricted to NASDAQ Stockholm equities, introducing a mid-cap bias and limiting generalizability to markets with different liquidity profiles, institutional settings, or levels of efficiency.
- **Windowing scheme.** Training and validation used overlapping 40-day windows with stride = 10, whereas test evaluation used stride = 1 to reflect deployment conditions where forecasts are produced daily. While realistic in practice, this design introduces serial dependence that can exaggerate predictive capacity; non-overlapping windows would provide a stricter robustness check.
- **Model class.** Only a bidirectional LSTM was tested. Conclusions therefore reflect the inductive biases of this architecture and may not transfer to alternatives such as convolutional or transformer-based networks.
- **Feature selection.** Greedy forward selection was used to demonstrate the taxonomy, excluding alternatives such as mutual information, SHAP-based importance, or PCA. Because BiLSTM training is stochastic and the signal is weak, the indicator-wise inclusion is path- and seed-dependent rather than unique. At the family level, using a greedy path instead of trying all group combinations further

limits exploration; under the observed instability, more exhaustive combinatorial testing at the family level could reveal alternative group combinations with stronger or more stable performance.

- **Evaluation fragility.** Substantial variance across seeds and folds indicated that small-sample effects can dominate outcomes in weak-signal domains. Forward selection emphasized validation peaks that did not reliably generalize to the test set, and cross-sectional hold-outs occasionally produced degenerate forecasts with positive R_{stock}^2 but little meaningful structure. Thus, all claims are framed as average tendencies over multiple runs/splits rather than guarantees for a single training instance
- **Temporal coverage.** CS-OOS/T-OOS evaluation was restricted to a single market sub-period. Since predictive signals are often regime-specific, repeating the analysis across several non-overlapping periods would provide a stronger test of robustness.

Taken together, these limitations underscore the need for stability analysis, alternative feature selection methods, and broader evaluation designs when drawing conclusions from weak-signal financial forecasting tasks.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Summary of Contributions

This thesis makes three main contributions to stock-return forecasting with technical indicators.

First, it introduces a taxonomy-driven, domain-informed approach to feature design. By grouping 24 single-asset technical indicators into Trend, Momentum, Volatility, and Volume families and using these families as an explicit constraint on feature selection, the study embeds interpretability into the model design rather than treating it as a post-hoc add-on. The taxonomy functions as a factor-like decomposition of technical indicators, clarifying where predictive content resides and where it fails to emerge.

Second, the empirical analysis on NASDAQ Stockholm equities shows that predictive power, while weak and unstable overall, is systematically concentrated in Volume and Volatility indicators and is highly sensitive to preprocessing choices. Universe-level normalization preserves a small but transferable cross-sectional signal, whereas per-stock and per-window normalization largely remove it, and repeated training runs reveal substantial variability in outcomes. These findings reinforce the view of technical signals as fragile but structured, and highlight the need for aggregation across seeds and careful validation–test design.

Third, the study operationalizes Murdoch et al.’s Predictive–Descriptive–Relevant (PDR) framework in a financial time-series setting. Taxonomy-constrained BiLSTM models achieve satisfactory predictive accuracy while improving descriptive accuracy through family-level selection patterns and maintaining practitioner relevancy at a 10-day horizon. Together, these contributions provide both an empirical benchmark for a mid-sized European market and a template for integrating domain structure and interpretability into technical-indicator-based forecasting.

6.2 Practical and Theoretical Implications

The findings have several implications for both practice and theory. For practitioners, the results suggest that compact, theory-guided subsets of indicators, particularly those drawn from the Volume and Volatility families, provide more stable and interpretable forecasts than models that indiscriminately include all available indicators. This offers a practical guideline for feature selection, emphasizing stability and transparency over maximal input complexity.

For academic research, the study demonstrates that interpretability can be operationalized through domain-informed structuring of the feature space. This complements post-hoc explanation techniques by embedding interpretability directly into the modeling process. The taxonomy approach illustrates that explanatory clarity can be achieved without sacrificing methodological rigor, aligning with recent calls in machine learning to treat interpretability as a design principle rather than an afterthought.

From a financial theory perspective, the results support the view that the weak-form efficient market hypothesis is imperfect. Small but systematic predictive signals were observed, although they remained fragile and unstable. This is consistent with prior evidence that technical analysis produces statistically significant but economically modest gains, often sensitive to methodology and sample design. The implication is that predictability exists, but only in narrow domains and under constrained conditions.

Finally, by framing interpretability as a structural design choice, the thesis addresses the concern raised by Lipton that interpretability claims are often vague or inconsistent,

providing a concrete and replicable example of how interpretability can be achieved in practice.

6.3 Future Work

Several avenues for future research follow from these findings.

- **Model diversity.** Comparing BiLSTM with alternative architectures such as CNNs, transformers, or hybrid models would clarify which inductive biases are most effective for weak-signal financial forecasting.
- **Feature-space exploration.** Extending beyond greedy forward selection, future work could apply mutual-information ranking, post-hoc attribution methods (e.g., SHAP, LIME), or representation learning (e.g., autoencoders) to test the stability of the taxonomy under richer selection regimes.
- **Cross-market generalization.** Replicating the taxonomy across other Nordic and global exchanges could distinguish universal signal structures from market-specific phenomena, particularly in settings with different liquidity and efficiency profiles.
- **Hybrid interpretability.** Combining taxonomy-driven grouping with post-hoc interpretability frameworks would provide both family-level structure and fine-grained attribution, strengthening the bridge between predictive modeling and financial decision support.

Closing Remarks

Overall, this study suggests that the main value of taxonomy-driven feature design in stock-return forecasting lies less in boosting predictive accuracy than in structuring a noisy indicator space so that weak signals become more interpretable. By embedding financial meaning into the modeling pipeline *ex ante* rather than relying solely on post-hoc explanations, the study illustrates how domain knowledge and interpretability can be integrated into machine-learning methods for financial prediction.

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A Complete Visualization of SEB Class A Stock Data

Dividends and stock splits appear sparse because they are infrequent events in daily data; since they were not used in model training, their absence does not affect the analysis. One missing value in absolute change is expected for the first row of the series, while the small proportion of zeros in relative change reflects regular days with both low trading volume and low volatility. All of these are normal occurrences in daily stock data.

Figure A.1: Complete visualization of SEB Class A stock